

1 **Occurrence and dissipation mechanisms of organic contaminants during sewage sludge**
2 **anaerobic digestion: A critical review**

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23 **ABSTRACT**

24 Sewage sludge contains contaminants of different types and is characterized by a large
25 number of pathogenic vectors. As a result, it must undergo treatment or stabilization (e.g.,
26 anaerobic digestion (AD)) before environmental disposal. AD-derived products (solid digestate
27 and liquid fraction) can be used as fertilizers. During this process, biogas is produced, and used
28 for energy purposes. All these components can be contaminated with various compounds,
29 whose amount depends on the feedstocks used in the process (and their mutual proportions).
30 This paper is a review of the studies dealing with the distribution of organic contaminants
31 between the individual phases (solid digestate, liquid fraction, and biogas) during sewage
32 sludge AD. Moreover, the mechanisms responsible for their dissipation are discussed and
33 further research prospects regarding the removal of contaminants during sewage sludge AD are
34 stressed.

35 AD proves to be an effective method for removing some groups of contaminants from
36 sewage sludge. Nonetheless, compounds such as benzotriazoles or per- and polyfluoroalkyl
37 substances are degraded to a small extent during AD, creating a potential risk to humans and
38 the environment. Contaminants are predominantly removed through biodegradation, but many
39 compounds, especially those with hydrophobic properties, are also sorbed onto digestate
40 particles. The process of sorption is suggested to reduce the bioavailability of contaminants. As
41 a result of sorption, contaminants accumulate in the largest amount in the solid digestate,
42 whereas in smaller amounts in the other AD products. Polar pharmaceuticals are particularly
43 leached, while volatile methylsiloxanes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, characterized
44 by a high Henry's law constant, are volatilized into the biogas. The removal of compounds can
45 be affected by AD operational parameters, the type of sludge, physicochemical properties of
46 contaminants, and sludge pretreatment used. The above-mentioned factors ultimately determine

47 their final concentration, persistence, and sorption potential as well as the formation of
48 metabolites.

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50 *Keywords:* Solid digestate; Liquid fraction; Biogas; Phase distribution; Biodegradation;
51 Volatilization

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67 1. Introduction

68 Sewage sludge is defined as solid or semi-solid waste generated at different stages of
69 wastewater treatment (Fijalkowski et al., 2017). It is a mixture of water and organic and
70 inorganic substances originating from municipal or industrial wastewater as well as rainwater
71 runoff from paved surfaces (Usman et al., 2012). Two main types of sewage sludge produced
72 in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are distinguished: primary sludge consisting of
73 suspended solids and organic matter, which accumulates in the primary sedimentation tank as
74 a result of gravitational sedimentation, and secondary sludge, which is produced with the
75 involvement of microorganisms (Lamastra et al., 2018). During wastewater treatment, organic
76 matter and nutrients, but also some contaminants, are not completely eliminated and due to this
77 they accumulate in the sewage sludge in the form of primary compounds or their metabolites
78 (Bauer et al., 2020).

79 One of the methods for utilizing sewage sludge is to apply into a soils. Nevertheless,
80 undesired organic contaminants, which are subject to strict controls, are a factor that inhibits
81 such use of sewage sludge (Fijalkowski et al., 2017). The disposal of untreated sewage sludge
82 into soil may contribute to the transfer of contaminants, which may ultimately get into
83 groundwater (Liew et al., 2022) or, as a result of surface runoff, into rivers and other water
84 bodies. When stored (e.g. in lagoons), sludge spontaneously undergoes anaerobic digestion. Its
85 consequence is the release of an unpleasant odor caused by the presence of volatile compounds,
86 such as hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) and ammonia (NH_3), in the released gas and the emission of
87 greenhouse gases, such as carbon dioxide (CO_2), methane (CH_4) (Zhu et al., 2016) and nitrous
88 oxide (N_2O). To mitigate these effects and recover the generated gas, controlled AD is
89 employed.

90 In the conventional AD process, stages occurring one after the other can be distinguished
 91 (**Fig. 1**), during which the electrons are transferred as a result of the development of anaerobic
 92 bacterial strains and their cooperation with one another (Appels et al., 2008). AD can be carried
 93 out at a mesophilic temperature (mesophilic anaerobic digestion, MAD, 35-45°C) (Obiukwu and
 94 Okafor, 2013) or a thermophilic temperature (thermophilic anaerobic digestion, TAD, 55-70°C)
 95 (Lin et al., 2018).

96
 97 **Fig. 1.** Biochemical processes and microorganisms involved in the AD of complex organic
 98 waste.

99 AD generates high energy products (biogas) and raw digestate, which is a liquid material
 100 that can be directly used as organic fertilizer (**Fig. 2**) (Akinbomi et al., 2022) or additionally
 101 separated into the solid and liquid fractions (Czekala et al., 2022). To dewater the raw digestate,
 102 mechanical separation is most frequently carried out using a press or a centrifuge, which allows
 103 the maximum dry matter content to be achieved at a level of 25-35% (Czekala et al., 2022). In
 104 terms of their composition, final AD products can be considered in three states of matter, i.e.

105 the biogas is analyzed in the gas phase, whereas the raw digestate, after the separation, both in
 106 the solid phase (solid digestate – after prior drying) and in the liquid phase (liquid fraction)
 107 (Fig. 2). Separation enables the possible directions of raw digestate disposal to be increased
 108 (Czekala et al., 2022).

109
 110 **Fig. 2.** Various types of sludge subjected to AD and its products.

111 The main property of the solid digestate is an increased content of organic matter and a
 112 higher phosphorus concentration compared to the liquid fraction (Kovačić et al., 2022). The
 113 solid digestate is a stabilized, fresh or dry product that can be directly used as a material to
 114 fertilize crops (Tambone et al., 2017), supplying nutrients, retaining water in the soil, and
 115 promoting the formation of humus (Czekala et al., 2022). It can also be a substrate for compost,
 116 being the main source of carbon and positively affecting its structural properties (Czekala et al.,
 117 2022).

118 The liquid fraction is an unused resource, rich in numerous micro- and macronutrients that
 119 are necessary to grow crops (Genz and Reemtsma, 2022). It is characterized by a low dry matter
 120 content, at a level of about 3%, and a low organic matter content (Herbes et al., 2020). It has

121 high dissolved potassium and nitrogen concentrations. Mineral nitrogen is concentrated mainly
122 as NH_3 (Kovačić et al., 2022). The liquid fraction is considered to have a greater importance
123 for fertilization, whereas the solid digestate contributes to greater changes in the soil
124 composition. However, in the AD process, the liquid fraction is most often returned for repeated
125 sewage treatment and stabilization. Such an operation promotes the effective use of water
126 resources (reducing the dry matter in the feedstock mixture) and provides beneficial
127 microorganisms to the AD process. The literature also indicates the possibility of using the
128 liquid fraction in soilless (hydroponic) cultivation (Kreuzig et al., 2021).

129 The biogas produced during AD contains on average 65-70 vol.% of CH_4 and 30-35 vol.%
130 of CO_2 (Mulchandani and Westerhoff, 2016). Most frequently, it is combusted to produce
131 electrical energy and heat. The benefits that the biogas generates for the process itself include,
132 in the first place, self-sufficiency in the supply of energy that is necessary to maintain the
133 temperature during AD and the related reduction in sewage sludge pretreatment costs
134 (Gebreeyessus and Jenicek, 2016).

135 Products obtained in the AD process (solid digestate, liquid fraction, and biogas) can
136 however contain harmful substances posing a threat to humans and the environment (Dragicevic
137 et al., 2018). Concerns related to the undesired content of contaminants require strict control of
138 these products before their reuse. In order to ensure the production of environmentally safe
139 solid digestate/liquid fraction, special attention should therefore be paid to feedstock selection,
140 bioreactor operating conditions, and pretreatment applied. Taking into account the fact that
141 contaminants present in sewage sludge may additionally have a harmful effect on the activity
142 of microorganisms involved in AD (Chen et al., 2008), the use of pretreatment of feedstock
143 before AD could be an interesting solution producing measurable benefits. It is also crucial to
144 understand the mechanisms responsible for the dissipation of specific groups of contaminants
145 during AD. This would allow for selecting appropriate process conditions to reduce the toxic

146 effect of the solid digestate/liquid fraction on the environment, while maintaining their
147 fertilizing qualities.

148 The aim of this study was to review the existing knowledge regarding the fate of different
149 contaminants present in sewage sludge during AD. In this research, special attention was paid
150 to the distribution of contaminants between all the AD products, i.e. solid digestate, liquid
151 fraction, and biogas. The present paper compares 23 groups of contaminants detected in the AD
152 products, including new emerging contaminants that are generated as a result of the socio-
153 economic development.

154

155 **2. Fate of contaminants during sewage sludge AD**

156 Depending on their persistence, contaminants occurring in the sewage sludge during AD
157 can be divided into three groups:

- 158 • less persistent contaminants, whose content generally decreases;
- 159 • medium persistent contaminants, whose content decreases or increases depending on
160 the specific chemical compound in a particular group;
- 161 • persistent contaminants, whose relative content remains at a constant level or increases.

162 **2.1. *Less persistent contaminants in solid digestate***

163 **2.1.1. *Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)***

164 PCBs are classified as persistent organic pollutants (Dąbrowska and Rosińska, 2012),
165 whose half-life times ($T_{1/2}$) in soil ranges from 1083 to 13750 days (Sinkkonen and Paasivirta,
166 2000). They are very stable in the environment and are difficult to degrade or undergo other
167 physical or chemical degradation processes (Montano et al., 2022). Nonetheless, studies

168 (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2007; Dąbrowska and Rosińska, 2012; Patureau and Trably, 2006)
169 show that PCBs can degrade when anaerobic conditions are maintained and in the presence of
170 specialized microorganisms. Most of the existing research mainly deals with priority PCB
171 congeners, which can be divided into lower chlorinated biphenyls (LCBs) - PCB 28 and PCB
172 52 - and higher chlorinated biphenyls (HCBs) - PCB 101, PCB 118, PCB 138, PCB 153, and
173 PCB 180, out of the 209 congeners found in the environment. In the solid digestate, LCBs and
174 HCBs are detected at a level of 0.0009 to 0.7 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S1**).

175 Patureau and Trably (2006) observed a small reduction (0.8-12%) in the content of PCBs
176 during MAD. The removal of PCBs was strongly correlated with a decrease in the content of
177 solids particles during AD. The low removal efficiency of PCBs was due to the low
178 bioavailability of these compounds, limited by their strong adsorption onto sludge particles.
179 Benabdallah El-Hadj et al. (2007) and Dąbrowska and Rosińska (2012) observed a much better
180 reduction of PCBs during AD, ranging from 8.3 to 100%, than the previously cited authors. The
181 T_{1/2} values calculated based on their study are in the range between 9 and 3277 days (**Table**
182 **S2**). The composition of individual PCBs in the digestate can be different relative to the sewage
183 sludge used and its structure. Benabdallah El-Hadj et al. (2007), for example, found the largest
184 amounts of PCB 101 and PCB 138 in the sludges and digestates, whereas in the study by
185 Dąbrowska and Rosińska (2012), these were PCB 28 and PCB 52. While Santos et al. (2007)
186 and Aparicio et al. (2009), identified only selected HCBs in the sludges and digestates. They
187 also found their increased concentrations in the digestates in comparison with the primary and
188 secondary sludges, which was explained by the concentration effect resulting from the digestate
189 dewatering process and by the too slow degradation of these compounds under anaerobic
190 conditions (Aparicio et al., 2009).

191 It is accepted that the quantitative composition of PCBs in the digestate is predominantly
192 affected by their chemical composition (the degree of PCB chlorination), but also by the process

193 temperature (MAD, TAD) and hydraulic retention time (HRT), i.e. the time that the sludge is
 194 in the anaerobic digester (**Fig. 3**) (Gerardi, 2003). It is also indicated that TAD shows a greater
 195 efficiency in removing HCB congeners (93-100%) than MAD (63-86%) (Benabdallah El-Hadj
 196 et al., 2007).

197

198 **Fig. 3.** Parameters affecting removal of organic compounds in solid digestate.

199 A lower content of PCBs in the digestate than in the sludge is associated with biotic
 200 processes (such as biodegradation) and abiotic processes (such as volatilization,
 201 photodegradation, or chemical combination with organic matter), which has been demonstrated
 202 in experiments conducted independently under biotic/abiotic conditions as well as abiotic
 203 conditions alone (Patureau and Trably, 2006). The proportion of biotic processes in the removal
 204 of PCBs is generally higher than that of abiotic ones. Moreover, PCB abiotic losses under
 205 anaerobic conditions are limited to an average value of 20%, which is considered to be
 206 substantial, but they are not the main effect of the process of PCBs removal during AD.
 207 According to some authors (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2007; Dąbrowska and Rosińska, 2012),
 208 the biodegradation of HCBs may take place under the influence of specialized groups of

209 microorganisms capable of conducting dechlorination of HCBs, which in effect leads to
210 obtaining LCBs. LCBs can therefore accumulate in the digestate because the biological
211 conversion of HCBs to LCBs is usually quicker than the subsequent biodegradation of LCBs
212 formed as a result of these transformations (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2007). Anaerobic
213 conditions promote transformations, in which chlorine is displaced by hydrogen (Wiegel and
214 Wu, 2000). The kinetics of the dechlorination process are dependent on the assemblage of
215 individual microbial populations present in the sewage sludges (Borja et al., 2005). The amount
216 of a given culture in the sewage sludge is influenced by the availability of sources of carbon,
217 hydrogen and other electron donors, the presence or absence of acceptors other than PCBs,
218 competition with other microorganisms, the presence of toxic contaminants and pH (Wiegel
219 and Wu, 2000). The process of dechlorination also depends on the saturation of PCB molecules
220 with chlorine (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2007). The percentage of chlorine removal from PCB
221 molecules characterized by a higher chlorination level is also found to be greater (Benabdallah
222 El-Hadj et al., 2007; Dąbrowska and Rosińska, 2012). Apart from the above-mentioned
223 environmental factors, the biodegradation of PCBs is also impacted by their molecule structure
224 especially isomerism (Borja et al., 2005). A study carried out by them demonstrated that the
225 chlorine atoms substituted in the *meta* and *para* positions are removed more easily and more
226 quickly as a result of their biodegradation. In the case of the *ortho* position, the biodegradation
227 of PCBs is inhibited. Dąbrowska and Rosińska (2012) suggest that apart from the above-
228 mentioned factors, the low content of HCBs compared to LCBs after AD is due to HCBs ability
229 to bioaccumulate on the account of their highly lipophilic nature (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al.,
230 2007). The accumulation of HCBs in microorganisms hinders their extraction (in accordance
231 with the principle that the more chlorine atoms in the biphenyl molecule, the better biosorption
232 (Borja et al., 2005), and hence the actual concentration of these compounds can be
233 underestimated to a certain degree.

234

235 2.1.2. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)

236 PAHs have a limited ability to degrade and their $T_{1/2}$ in soil ranges from 35 to 495 days
237 (Agarry and Oghenejoboh, 2015; Oleszczuk and Baran, 2003). On the other hand, it is accepted
238 that AD is generally a process that promotes the biodegradation of PAHs from the sewage
239 sludge (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2006; Siebielska, 2014; Trably et al., 2003), with their
240 removal efficiency rate ranging between 5.9 and 93% ($T_{1/2}$ = 6-87 days, **Table S2**). The total
241 PAH concentrations in the solid digestate range from 0.5 to 6.5 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S1**). In addition
242 to the above-mentioned properties of the feedstock used during the process (which has also
243 been observed in the case of PCBs), the range of PAH removal can also be affected by AD
244 temperature. Trably et al. (2003) compared the PAH removal efficiencies for the bioreactors
245 operating under the MAD and TAD conditions. The authors found that the process exhibited a
246 higher efficiency in removing PAHs (especially the heaviest ones) under TAD conditions than
247 under MAD. During MAD, the removal of PAHs takes place as a result of a specific biological
248 activity, whereas the higher removal rate of the lightest PAHs is due to abiotic losses. The
249 removal of PAHs was significantly enhanced in the bioreactor operating under the TAD system
250 as a result of a substantial increase in abiotic losses of 3-ring PAHs as well as due to an elevated
251 mass transfer diffusion rate and a greater bioavailability of the heavier PAHs (5- and 6-ring) at
252 a higher temperature.

253 Nonetheless, the study results (Aparicio et al., 2009; Pigoli et al., 2021) reveal that during
254 AD the content of PAHs in digestates can also increase. Al Seadi et al. (2013) suggest that the
255 type of sludge used can affect the increase in PAH content during AD. In turn, Aparicio et al.
256 (2009) explain the increase in the content of PAHs in the digestate by their slow degradation
257 during the process and the concentration effect of digestate dewatering.

258 Włodarczyk-Makuła (2008) obtained different results. This author observed an about 2-fold
259 increase in the content of $\Sigma 16$ PAHs after 7 days of AD, which was primarily associated with
260 an increase in the content of 3- and 4-ring PAHs caused by the release of these hydrocarbons
261 from the organic matrix. An extension of AD to 21 days resulted in a decrease in the content of
262 the PAHs studied to the level from the beginning of the experiment. This indicates that under
263 conditions of deficiency of an easily available organic substrate, the PAHs were the main source
264 of carbon and energy for microorganisms. Włodarczyk-Makuła (2008) explains that the
265 decrease in the PAH concentrations during AD could have resulted from both biotic
266 (biodegradation) and abiotic processes (sorption, the volatilization of hydrocarbons with a high
267 value of gas pressure, and the formation of transformed PAH derivatives as a result of reactions
268 with other compounds).

269 In the literature, there are divergent data regarding the parameters affecting the quantitative
270 variation of PAHs during AD. Generally, they are the following (**Fig. 3**): process temperature
271 (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2006; Trably et al., 2003), PAH molecular mass (Benabdallah El-
272 Hadj et al., 2006; Siebielska, 2014; Trably et al., 2003; Włodarczyk-Makuła, 2008), HRT
273 (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2006), and the degree of microbial acclimation (Trably et al.,
274 2003). Chang et al. (2003), however, challenge the impact of molecular mass and suggest that
275 the main parameters include the type of sludge used during the process and adaptation
276 conditions applied with respect to it, i.e. pH, suspension concentration, and the presence of
277 different electron-donating substituents, electron acceptors, and surface active agents. This is
278 confirmed by the study of Trably et al. (2003), who demonstrated that the removal of PAHs
279 required long-lasting acclimation of methanogenic microorganisms. This was indicated by a
280 much lower efficiency of PAH removal during MAD by the non-adapted ecosystem in
281 comparison with the bacterial consortium adapted to biodegradation of PAHs.

282 Benabdallah El-Hadj et al. (2006) and Trably et al. (2003) observed a higher removal
283 efficiency of PAHs from the sludge during TAD (53-65%) compared to MAD (43-46%), which
284 was primarily related to the removal of 2- and 3-ring PAHs (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2006)
285 or 4- to 6-ring PAHs (Trably et al., 2003). The removal effect of individual PAHs depended on
286 HRT (Benabdallah El-Hadj et al., 2006). A higher HRT caused a more effective elimination of
287 these compounds. In an experimental study by Siebielska (2014), the extent of reduction of the
288 individual PAHs ranged from 39 to 48% and was clearly dependent on the number of rings in
289 the molecule. According to the 2nd-order kinetic model, the 5- and 6-ring PAHs were
290 characterized by the slowest degradation.

291

292 2.1.3. *Pharmaceuticals (PHACs)*

293 Commonly occurring contaminants in digestates are PHACs. Ibuprofen (IBP) is among the
294 most frequently encountered PHACs in the solid fraction of digestate (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016;
295 Samaras et al., 2014), which is attributed to its widespread use due to its analgesic and anti-
296 inflammatory properties (Aguilar-Romero et al., 2024).

297 The concentrations of PHACs in the solid digestate are in the range from 0.0005 to 0.69 mg
298 kg⁻¹ (**Table S1**). During AD, these compounds may remain in an unchanged form or undergo
299 partial or complete degradation, depending on their physicochemical properties and the sludge
300 characteristics (Carballa et al., 2006; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Malmborg and Magnér, 2015;
301 Samaras et al., 2014). Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) obtained the biotransformation of fluoxetine
302 (FLX) and citalopram (CTL) at a level of 35-73% and 14-48%, respectively. On the other hand,
303 Malmborg and Magnér (2015) as well as Taboada-Santos et al. (2019) recorded a relatively
304 lower degradation of FLX (0-32%) and a higher degradation of CTL (23-85%) than the
305 previously cited authors. It was also observed that AD has a high impact on the degradation of

306 naproxen (NPX) (76-91%) (Carballa et al., 2006; Samaras et al., 2014; Taboada-Santos et al.,
307 2019) and ketoprofen (KPF) (83-94%) (Samaras et al., 2014). Carbamazepine (CBZ), in turn,
308 is removed only to a small extent (2-28%) or is not removed at all during AD (Carballa et al.,
309 2006; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Malmborg and Magnér, 2015; Taboada-Santos et al., 2019). A
310 varied removal range has also been observed in the case of diclofenac (DCF) (Malmborg and
311 Magnér, 2015), ibuprofen (IBP) (Carballa et al., 2006; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Malmborg
312 and Magnér, 2015), and diazepam (DZM) (Carballa et al., 2006; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016). For
313 example, Samaras et al. (2014) and Taboada-Santos et al. (2019), showed the elimination of
314 IBP to be at a level of 73-94%, whereas Samaras et al. (2014) and Carballa et al. (2006) found
315 the elimination of DCF to range 60-96%. Moreover, Taboada-Santos et al. (2019) obtained a
316 74% removal efficiency for DZM. The reasons for this divergence for a particular compound
317 remain unclear.

318 All researchers analyzing PHACs during MAD and TAD (Carballa et al., 2006; Gonzalez-
319 Gil et al., 2016; Malmborg and Magnér, 2015; Samaras et al., 2014) are in agreement that
320 temperature does not influence the removal of PHACs in the AD process. Also, most of the
321 researchers (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2016) observed no effect of the solids
322 retention time (SRT), i.e. the average time that bacteria (solids) are in the anaerobic digester
323 (Gerardi, 2003). Yang et al. (2016) explain the absence of a significant relationship between
324 SRT and the removal of PHACs by the fact that these compounds are not the main substrates
325 in the AD process. In turn Samaras et al. (2014), found that the removal of most of the PHACs
326 increased only slightly due to an increase in SRT. In testing the effect of (thermal or alkaline)
327 sludge pretreatment on the removal of PHACs during AD, Carballa et al. (2006) observed that
328 the degree of removal increased only for IBP in the case of the thermally pretreated sludge. In
329 carrying out thermal hydrolysis of the sludge as pretreatment, Taboada-Santos et al. (2019)
330 showed that it did not affect significantly the biotransformation efficiency of PHACs during

331 AD. It was also proven that the type of the AD system used (single-stage mesophilic or
332 thermophilic AD and two-stage thermophilic/mesophilic AD) did not influence the removal of
333 nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs such as DCF, NPX, IBP, and KPF (Samaras et al., 2014).

334 Because there are divergent results regarding the removal efficiency of PHACs during AD,
335 the mechanisms and factors responsible for their removal cannot be understood unambiguously.
336 Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) suggest that one of the reasons for the observed differences could be
337 the form of binding of PHACs with the sludge (**Fig. 3**). PHACs freshly added to the sludge
338 (more weakly bound to the matrix) behave differently than compounds accumulated in it (native
339 compounds that are more strongly bound). Therefore, the degradation of more strongly bound
340 compounds will be more difficult due to their lower bioavailability, and hence they are more
341 difficult to biodegrade than weakly bound compounds (Dictor et al., 2003). Yang et al. (2016)
342 also explain that PHACs with electron-donating functional groups (e.g. NPX, atenolol (ATN),
343 caffeine, paracetamol (PCM), amitriptyline) are easily removed in the AD process. On the other
344 hand, PHACs with strong electron-withdrawing functional groups (e.g. DCF, CBZ, gemfibrozil
345 (GEM)) are resistant to degradation during AD. Furthermore, differences between countries,
346 seasonal consumption, and especially process conditions are additionally mentioned as factors
347 contributing to the observed differences in the results regarding the removal of PHACs during
348 AD (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Samaras et al., 2014).

349 Carballa et al. (2008), Malmborg and Magnér (2015), Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016), Yang et
350 al. (2016), and Ali et al. (2019) analyzed the solid digestate and additionally the liquid fraction
351 in terms of their PHAC content. The distribution of PHACs between the fractions was assessed
352 by calculating the partition coefficients K_d and K_{oc} for them (Ali et al., 2019; Carballa et al.,
353 2008; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016). Moreover, the octanol-water distribution constant ($\log D$) and
354 the octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log P$) are commonly used to evaluate the distribution
355 of PHACs to determine the solubility of substances in polar and non-polar phases (Ali et al.,

2019; Malmborg and Magnér, 2015). K_d indicates the ratio of the concentration of a substance adsorbed onto a solid to the concentration of the substance dissolved in water. K_d values > 1 ($\log K_d > 0$) show the greater affinity of a given compound for the solid digestate than for the liquid fraction. K_{oc} , in turn, describes the ratio of the concentration of a substance adsorbed onto the organic fraction to the concentration of the substance dissolved in water. Compounds with low values of the coefficients $\log D$, $\log P$ and $\log K_{oc}$ are expected to have a greater affinity for the liquid fraction, whereas substances with high values of these coefficients will be sorbed onto solid particles in the solid digestate (Ali et al., 2019). Agreement can be seen in the literature as to the enhanced affinity of PHACs for the solid phase (Ali et al., 2019; Carballa et al., 2007; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Malmborg and Magnér, 2015), which is associated with the hydrophobic nature of these compounds (Yang et al., 2016) and their strong adsorption capacity (Malmborg and Magnér, 2015). It was shown that CTL and FLX were associated with the digestate solid phase in 90% ($\log K_d > 1.5$) (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016). Similar results were obtained by Malmborg and Magnér (2015) for CTL, FLX, and sertraline, which were detected at a level of 90-99% in the solid phase.

The content of antibiotics in the solid digestate is in the range from 0.002 to 1.708 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S1**). These compounds can significantly influence the AD process due to their antibacterial nature (Xiao et al., 2021). It is commonly accepted that the concentration of antibiotics in the sewage sludge can be substantially reduced through AD, but they cannot be eliminated completely (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Lehmann and Bloem, 2021). The potential of AD to degrade and remove antibiotics largely depends on the concentration and class of antibiotic, the type of feedstock, and inoculum sources, but also on bioreactor operating conditions (Massé et al., 2014).

Analyzing the effect of AD on the persistence of 7 antibiotics used in livestock farming, Lehmann and Bloem (2021) observed a decrease in content of sulfadiazine (SDZ),

381 ciprofloxacin (CIP), tetracycline (TC) and enrofloxacin (ENR). AD was the most effective in
382 reducing the content of ENR (100%) and SDZ (98%), whereas TC (30%) and CIP (14%) were
383 characterized by a lower removal level during AD. The authors (Lehmann and Bloem, 2021)
384 explain these trends by the persistence of these antibiotics. TC, CIP, and ENR are considered
385 to be very persistent antibiotics ($T_{1/2}$ in soil from 578 to 3466 days (Walters et al., 2010)). SDZ,
386 in turn, is classified as medium persistent (Massé et al., 2014) ($T_{1/2}$ in soil from 57 to 237 days
387 (Yang et al., 2009)). The complete elimination of ENR during AD resulted from its very low
388 original content in the sludge ($< 0.04 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$). The studies by Carballa et al. (2006), Malmborg
389 and Magnér (2015), Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016), and Yang et al. (2016) concerned antibiotics
390 typically used in the treatment of humans. Carballa et al. (2006) noted that sulfamethoxazole
391 (SMX) and roxithromycin (ROX) were removed from the sludge during AD at a very high level
392 (85-99%), which is also confirmed by the studies of other authors (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016;
393 Taboada-Santos et al., 2019). Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) observed that a high ROX removal
394 efficiency was exclusively found during the autumn period, whereas in the spring
395 thrimethoprim (TMP) was removed better. Other authors also confirm the effectiveness of AD
396 in removing TMP from sludge (Malmborg and Magnér, 2015; Taboada-Santos et al., 2019;
397 Yang et al., 2016) .

398 Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) claim that the effectiveness of AD in removing antibiotics is
399 determined by the contact time of an antibiotic with the organic matrix of the sludge (freshly
400 added/aged) (**Fig. 3**). Process temperature (Carballa et al., 2006; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016),
401 SRT (Carballa et al., 2006; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2016), organic loading rate
402 (OLR), which is determined as organic matter feed-in per unit time and volume of the reactor,
403 the type of pretreatment used (Carballa et al., 2006; Taboada-Santos et al., 2019), and phase
404 distribution (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016) have not generally been observed to significantly
405 influence the removal of antibiotics from the sludge during AD. Exceptions have been reported

406 for few antibiotics, such as ROX and TMP. Carballa et al. (2006) noted that alkaline treatment
407 of the sludge negatively affected the removal of ROX during MAD in comparison to TAD.
408 Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) claim that the effect of SRT and OLR on the removal of TMP and
409 ROX was significant during both MAD and TAD. In the case of AD carried out in the spring
410 period, when a higher SRT was applied, the average biotransformation of TMP analyzed in the
411 solid fraction of the sludge was higher (80-82%) than in the case of AD during the autumn
412 period (26-32%). ROX, in turn, was removed not earlier than the autumn period, which
413 probably resulted from the higher OLR. Furthermore, Yang et al. (2016) indicate the molecular
414 structure of compounds (e.g. the presence/absence of strong electron-withdrawing functional
415 groups or strong electron-donating functional groups) as a factor responsible for the effective
416 removal of antibiotics from the sludge solid fraction during AD. TMP has an amino group that
417 is a unique electron donor and due to this it is effectively removed during AD.

418 It is accepted that the main mechanisms responsible for the removal of PHACs during AD
419 are biodegradation (Samaras et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2016), biotransformation (Gonzalez-Gil
420 et al., 2016), and strong adsorption in the sludge (Malmborg and Magnér, 2015), limiting their
421 extraction and hence enhancing the effectiveness of their removal. Therefore, immobilization
422 of PHACs in the sludge is not a process leading to their physical removal, but only contributes
423 to a reduction in the risk associated with their presence in the environment. Attention should
424 also be paid to the fact that during biotransformation the formation of metabolites may occur,
425 which may have different environmental impacts. Nevertheless, studies of this kind are scarce.
426 Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2019) described the enzymatic mechanisms of the transformation of 35
427 organic contaminants found in the digestate under anaerobic conditions. The extraction of
428 natural enzymes from the digestate showed that these compounds had been substantially
429 biodegraded (> 20%) (PCM, CTL, ATN, SMX, acetyl-SMX, clarithromycin, erythromycin,
430 climbazole, and terbutryn undergo enzymatic reactions).

431

432 2.1.4. Hydrocarbons

433 Total hydrocarbons (THs) include both hydrocarbons of anthropogenic origin, mainly
434 aliphatic and polyaromatic petroleum hydrocarbons (PHs), and hydrocarbons of biogenic
435 origin, i.e. natural waxes secreted by plants (De Simone et al., 2022; Huynh et al., 2011). Some
436 aliphatic and polyaromatic PHs are highly toxic and characterized by low biodegradability and
437 high lipophilicity, and hence they are classified as persistent organic pollutants (Moreda et al.,
438 1998), with their $T_{1/2}$ in soil ranging between 60 and 500 days (Kuran et al., 2014). In terms of
439 the carbon atom chain length, the range of determination of PHs is usually from C_{10} (n-decane)
440 to C_{40} (n-tetracontane), which includes the lighter PHs (C_{10} - C_{18} fraction) and the heavier PHs
441 (C_{19} - C_{40} fraction). The TH content in the solid digestate is very high (13029-15579 $mg\ kg^{-1}$),
442 with the content of C_{10} - C_{40} PHs ranging between 284 and 6715 $mg\ kg^{-1}$ (**Table S1**).

443 De Simone et al. (2022) demonstrated that MAD affected the degradation of C_{10} - C_{40} PHs
444 (45%) to a greater extent than in the case of THs (30%) (**Fig. 3**). The calculated $T_{1/2}$ values for
445 C_{10} - C_{40} PHs range from 33 to 92 days (**Table S2**). Although the conditioning of the sludge with
446 cationic polyelectrolyte caused a 2-fold decrease in the concentration of THs and C_{10} - C_{40} PHs,
447 MAD caused their content in the digestate to increase (by 13%). AD of the sludges (initial and
448 conditioned) led to the similar final contents of THs and C_{10} - C_{40} PHs in the digestates.
449 However, the fraction of the heavier PHs was successfully degraded in both sludge types and
450 partially transformed into the lighter PHs. The presence of the lighter PHs in the digestates
451 suggests that they are characterized by exceptionally low biodegradability and/or
452 bioavailability under anaerobic conditions (De Simone et al., 2022). Pigoli et al. (2021), in turn,
453 observed after the TAD process a substantial reduction in PHs C_{10} - C_{40} (by 65%) in the digested
454 sewage sludge with the addition of sludge from the agro-food industry and the liquid fraction

455 of food waste. The observed differences between the above-mentioned authors probably result
456 from the use of sludges of different origin. In the case of De Simone et al. (2022), the lower
457 removal efficiency of C₁₀-C₄₀ PHs from the sewage sludge during AD could have been affected
458 by the municipal/industrial sludge that was applied, whereas the use of sludge of biological
459 origin was probably responsible for the higher degradation found by Pigoli et al. (2021).

460

461 **2.2. *Medium persistent contaminants in solid digestate***

462 **2.2.1. *Bisphenol A (BPA)***

463 BPA is used to stabilize produced plastics, including polycarbonate, and epoxy resins. Due
464 to its structure similar to estrogen, BPA is considered to be an endocrine-active compound
465 impacting the human hormonal balance (Vasiljevic and Harner, 2021). The BPA content in the
466 solid digestate is in the range between 0.69 and 1.89 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S3**).

467 To date, there have been few studies on the effect of AD on BPA degradation. Samaras et
468 al. (2014) found that BPA is removed during both TAD and MAD, in the range from 56 to 64%,
469 but MAD is characterized by a higher removal efficiency (**Fig. 3**). However, these authors
470 demonstrated that enhanced effectiveness of BPA removal (up to 72%) during AD can be
471 achieved by combining thermophilic and mesophilic bioreactors. According to Samaras et al.
472 (2014), the mechanism responsible for the removal of BPA during AD is chiefly
473 biodegradation. On the other hand, Yang, et al. (2016) observed that in spite of the presence of
474 a hydroxyl group (which could theoretically act as an electron donor) in the molecule of BPA,
475 it is not removed during MAD. But these authors suggested that the observed absence of BPA
476 reduction could have been caused by the system's secondary contamination with this compound
477 as a result of its release from the plastic components of the experimental system.

478

479 2.2.2. Phthalic acid esters (PAEs)

480 PAEs are used as plasticizers to improve the elasticity of plastics and are an additive to
481 cosmetics, glues, and paints (Armstrong et al., 2018; Marttinen et al., 2003). They include a
482 group of 22 compounds of varying properties (Ghosh and Sahu, 2022). Similarly to BPA, they
483 exhibit effects that disrupt the functioning of the hormonal and reproductive systems (Wang
484 and Qian, 2021). Moreover, these compounds have an ability to accumulate in solids due to
485 their lipophilic properties (Aparicio et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2020). The concentration of PAEs
486 in the solid digestate is in the range from 0.152 to 280 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S3**).

487 Marttinen et al. (2003) found that the AD process contributes only to partial removal of
488 bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) from the sludge (9.5%). Aparicio et al. (2009), in turn,
489 recorded an increase in the DEHP content in the dewatered digested sludge (**Fig. 3**). This
490 indicates the low degradation of DEHP under anaerobic conditions and its concentration
491 capacity after the dewatering process (Aparicio et al., 2009). The concentration effect was also
492 demonstrated by Armstrong et al. (2018), who analyzed both dewatered and non-dewatered
493 digestates in terms of their content of DEHP, diisononyl phthalate (DiNP), diisodecyl phthalate
494 (DiDP), and benzyl butyl phthalate (BBP). These researchers found a decrease in the
495 concentrations of all the compounds analyzed (32-74%) in the non-dewatered digestate. A
496 similar phenomenon was not observed in the case of the dewatered digestate, in which an
497 increase in the content of these PAEs was recorded, ranging from 2 to 56%. The application of
498 more advanced AD processes (sludge pretreatment: thermal hydrolysis or a two-phase acid/gas
499 process) also led to an elevated concentration of most of the PAEs. The thermal hydrolysis or
500 two-phase acid/gas process caused an increase in the concentration of DEHP, DiNP and DiDP
501 in the non-dewatered digestate (from 51 to 184%) and in the dewatered digestate (from 60 to

502 261%). As far as BBP is concerned, a favorable situation was observed in the case of both
503 processes, as a result of which it was degraded (a reduction at a level of 21-76% or 11-66%
504 prior to and after dewatering, respectively).

505 The main processes responsible for reducing DEHP content during AD are biodegradation
506 (Armstrong et al., 2018; Santos et al., 2007) and strong adsorption by organic matter
507 (predominantly volatile suspended solids) (Marttinen et al., 2003). Nevertheless, as mentioned
508 before, the latter process is not physical degradation of a contaminant, but only a “masking” of
509 its content in the solid digestate. The biodegradation yield of DEHP depends on its
510 bioavailability, which is limited by its transfer in the sewage sludge (Fountoulakis et al., 2006).
511 Armstrong et al. (2018) claim that the decrease in the concentrations of PAEs after AD in their
512 study was not significant, which was probably due to the analysis of stored samples, in which
513 PAEs were strongly bound to the matrix.

514

515 2.2.3. *Nonylphenol (NP) and its derivatives*

516 Similarly as the previously mentioned contaminants, NP and its derivatives, i.e. NP
517 ethoxylates (NP₁₋₁₂EO) and NP ethoxycarboxylates (NPEC), are included in compounds that
518 disrupt the functioning of the hormonal system. These compounds are found in the solid
519 digestate in concentrations ranging between 0.21 and 1385 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S3**).

520 NP₁₋₁₂EO content has been shown to decrease after AD. Samaras et al. (2014) observed that
521 NP monoethoxylate (NP₁EO) and NP diethoxylate (NP₂EO) (28-87%) were removed in
522 mesophilic, thermophilic, and two-stage thermophilic/mesophilic continuous flow reactors.
523 Santos et al. (2007) found a partial reduction in the NP₁EO and NP₂EO content in the digested
524 sludge in comparison with the non-stabilized primary and secondary sludges, whereas opposite
525 relationships were observed by González et al. (2010). Aparicio et al. (2009) showed a complete

526 removal of NP₂EO, with a simultaneous increase in NP₁EO content after AD. Paterakis et al.
527 (2012), on the other hand, found the removal of NP polyethoxylates (NP₃₋₁₂EO) to be at a level
528 of 66-83%, while NP₁₋₂EO at a level of 88-100%, but only in some experimental treatments. In
529 most of the digestates, NP was present in the highest concentrations (131-1385 mg kg⁻¹)
530 (Aparicio et al., 2009; González et al., 2010; Santos et al., 2007), which was associated with an
531 increased content of this compound as a result of AD. In turn, different results were obtained
532 by other authors (Paterakis et al., 2012; Samaras et al., 2014), who found the biodegradation of
533 NP during AD to be at a level of 50-100%. Furthermore, the authors (Paterakis et al., 2012)
534 showed the NPEC content to increase (215-1000%) in most of the digested sludges.

535 Samaras et al. (2014) mention the type of the AD system used as the main factor
536 contributing to a reduction in the content of NP, NP₁EO and NP₂EO in the sludge (**Fig. 3**).
537 Higher removal rates of the above-mentioned contaminants are observed under the two-stage
538 system (58-87%) than in the single-stage one (28-59%). Samaras et al. (2014) also found that
539 the biotransformation of NP and its derivatives in the bioreactor process is affected by the
540 temperature applied. Under the MAD system, the removal of NP₁EO (36%) and the
541 accumulation of NP (an increase by 7.5%) occurred, whereas under the TAD system the
542 removal of NP (59%) and the accumulation of NP₁EO (an increase by 45%) were observed. In
543 the case of NP₂EO, a higher reduction was found under TAD conditions (57%) relative to MAD
544 (28%). Furthermore, the researchers also noted that the digesters' operation at a higher SRT
545 resulted in a better removal efficiency of these compounds. Paterakis et al. (2012), in turn,
546 showed a better removal of NPEOs from a mixture of primary and secondary sludge than for
547 the primary sludge.

548 The increase in the content of NP, NP₁EO and NP₂EO observed in the above-mentioned
549 studies is explained by the concentration effect caused by the organic matter loss during AD
550 (González et al., 2010) or by the process of dehydration of the digested sludge (Aparicio et al.,

551 2009). Another possible mechanism responsible for the increased content of these compounds
552 can be degradation under anaerobic conditions/biodegradation of the higher NP₃₋₁₂EO
553 compounds to lower ones (Paterakis et al., 2012). This process starts in the hydrophilic part of
554 the molecule and leads to the loss of ethoxylate groups. As a result of that, the ethoxylate chain
555 of NP₃₋₁₂EO is shortened until NP₂EO is formed (Ahel et al., 1994). The increase after AD in
556 the content of NPECs, being the breakdown byproducts of NP₃₋₁₂EO (Paterakis et al.,
557 2012), confirms such a pathway of reduction in the content of these compounds. During the
558 further stage of AD, NP₂EO is degraded to NP₁EO, while subsequently NP₁EO to NP (Aparicio
559 et al., 2009; Knudsen et al., 2000; Minamiyama et al., 2006; Patureau et al., 2008; Samaras et
560 al., 2014). The stability of these compounds increases with the decreasing length of the
561 ethoxylate chain (González et al., 2010; Paterakis et al., 2012). According to Janex-Habibi et
562 al. (2009), NP is not further transformed and accumulates in biosolids. It is also suggested
563 (Stasinakis, 2012) that the biodegradation of NP under anaerobic conditions is slower than its
564 formation as a result of the biodegradation of NP₁₋₁₂EO, which can also be responsible for the
565 elevated NP content in some of the studies.

566

567 2.2.4. Estrogens

568 The concentration of estrogens in the solid digestate is in the range of 0.0015-0.549 mg kg⁻¹
569 ¹ (Table S3). In the literature, there are divergent results as to the fate of estrogens during AD.
570 This is probably due to the difficulty of estrogens analysis in the sludge, an ambiguous behavior
571 of their conjugates, or the selected AD conditions. The results obtained by Ternes et al. (2002),
572 Andersen et al. (2003), and Taboada-Santos et al. (2019) indicate the ineffectiveness of AD in
573 removing estrogens. The concentration of estrone (E1), 17β-estradiol (E2) and synthetic 17α-
574 ethinylestradiol (EE2) in the digestate usually exceeded their initial content in the sludge. The

575 study by Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) also reveal the high persistence of E1 and E2 during AD.
576 However, these authors recorded a 74-100% biotransformation for EE2. During AD of the
577 primary sludge or a mixture of primary and secondary sludge, Paterakis et al. (2012) found a
578 conversion of E1 to E2 (a decrease in E1 content by 68-96% and an increase in E2 content by
579 324-621%). Furthermore, they noted that the content of EE2 (4-43%), estriol (E3) (4-45%) and
580 estrone sulfate conjugate (E1-S3) (21-36%) decreased during AD. Using spiked compounds to
581 the sludge, Carballa et al. (2006), in turn, observed that the removal rate was at a level of 85%
582 for $\Sigma E1 + E2$ and 75-85% for EE2.

583 According to Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) and Paterakis et al. (2012), process temperature has
584 a significant impact on the fate of some estrogens during AD (**Fig. 3**), which is not confirmed
585 by the study by Carballa et al. (2006). Paterakis et al. (2012) indicate that apart from
586 temperature, the type of sludge also determines the rate of transformation of E1 into E2.
587 Furthermore, Paterakis et al. (2012) showed that SRT has a significant effect on reducing E1 to
588 E2, but it cannot be isolated from the temperature effect. A similar phenomenon was not
589 observed by Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) and Carballa et al. (2006), who demonstrated, in turn,
590 that SRT had no impact on the removal of estrogens. Additionally, sludge pretreatment did not
591 contribute to enhanced estrogen biotransformation efficiency during AD, either (Taboada-
592 Santos et al., 2019). According to Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016), OLR and the partition into the
593 fractions (solid/liquid) do not also contribute to the removal of estrogens during AD.

594 Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) think that an increase in E1 and E2 content can be due to the
595 deconjugation of the conjugates E1 and E2 present in the sludge, which is confirmed by the
596 study conducted by Paterakis et al. (2012). These authors observed the concentration of the
597 conjugate E1-3S to decrease, which may indicate its deconjugation and thus conversion to E1.
598 Moreover, Paterakis et al. (2012) claim that under anaerobic conditions the biotransformation
599 of E1 and E2 occurs during AD until an equilibrium is reached between them. The mutual

600 biological transformation of E1 and E2 is dependent on their initial concentrations in the sludge.
601 At a higher initial concentration, E1 is reduced to E2 (Paterakis et al., 2012), but when a higher
602 concentration of E2 is dominant, it is oxidized to E1 (Czajka and Londry, 2006). Furthermore,
603 Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) demonstrated that E1 and E2 are primarily associated with the solid
604 digestate (84-92%), whereas a reverse situation was observed for EE2.

605

606 2.2.5. *Musk fragrances and personal care products*

607 The content of musk fragrances in the solid digestate is in the range from 0.01 to 13.92 mg
608 kg⁻¹ (**Table S3**). Some studies (Clara et al., 2011; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016) reveal that AD is
609 ineffective in removing synthetic musk fragrances from sewage sludge or removes it to a small
610 extent. Clara et al. (2011) did not observe most of the musk fragrances to be removed (an
611 increase by 13-97%) or the removal was marginal in the case of traesolide (ATII) (16%).
612 Likewise, Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) demonstrated that galaxolide (HHCB) and tonalide
613 (AHTN) were not eliminated during AD (a reduction \leq 16% or an increase by 37-475%,
614 depending on the sludge sampling time). A slightly higher reduction and a lower increase in the
615 content of these compounds were recorded for MAD than under TAD conditions (Gonzalez-
616 Gil et al., 2016). The removal effectiveness is however affected by the form of occurrence of
617 compounds in the sludge (**Fig. 3**). Studies conducted using spiked compounds in the sludges
618 show that they can be removed during AD (Carballa et al., 2007; Taboada-Santos et al., 2019).
619 Carballa et al. (2008) recorded the removal of spiked HHCB and AHTN during AD at a level
620 of 60-67%. Nonetheless, degradation was not dependent on AD and SRT temperature (Carballa
621 et al., 2007). Taboada-Santos et al. (2019) also showed a high biotransformation efficiency for
622 spiked HHCB (70%) and AHTN (59%) during AD. The applied pretreatment (thermal
623 hydrolysis) reduced the removal efficiency of these compounds.

624 Personal care products are, however, a more numerous group of contaminants in the solid
625 digestate (0.107-63 mg kg⁻¹, **Table S3**). Studies dealing with disinfectants (triclosan (TCS),
626 triclocarban (TCC)) have demonstrated different behaviors of these compounds during AD.
627 Yang et al. (2016) did not find TCS to be removed after AD, which is also confirmed by the
628 studies conducted by Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) and Heidler and Halden (2009), who observed
629 the accumulation of TCS in the digested sludges. On the contrary, Samaras et al. (2014)
630 revealed that TCS was removed at a level of 46 and 62% during MAD and TAD, respectively,
631 or 78% under the two-stage thermophilic/mesophilic system. In the case of TCC, the AD
632 process proved to be ineffective in removing this compound from the sludges (Heidler and
633 Halden, 2009) or led to its accumulation in the digestate (Yang et al., 2016).

634 The analysis of the distribution profiles of the contaminants described revealed that 90% of
635 HHCB and 100% of AHTN and TCS were related to the solid digestate (Gonzalez-Gil et al.,
636 2016). It was observed differently in the case of an UV blocker, octocrylene (OCR), which
637 exhibited a low affinity for the solid fraction (Ali et al., 2019).

638

639 2.2.6. *Other contaminants*

640 Linear alkylbenzene sulfonates (LASs) are one of the most frequently used synthetic surface
641 active agents, which are a component of many detergents and cleaning agents (Gouda et al.,
642 2022). Their content in the solid digestate is in the range from 267 to 10126 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table**
643 **S3**). Based on a laboratory study, Aparicio et al. (2009) claim that LASs are poorly degraded
644 during AD. This fact, coupled with the sludge mass loss as a result of organic matter degradation
645 during AD and dewatering of the digestate, causes an increase in the concentration of LASs in
646 the digestate compared to the primary and secondary sludge (Aparicio et al., 2009). Using
647 spiked LASs, García et al. (2005) also confirmed their poor biodegradation during AD.

648 According to the above-cited authors (García et al., 2005), LASs are also sorbed onto solids of
649 the digestate formed, i.e. the concentration of LASs in the solid digestate increases with an
650 increase in the alkyl chain length/degree of hydrophobicity of a compound.

651 As regards organotins, an analysis was performed on monobutyltin (MBT) and dibutyltin
652 (DBT), being thermal and light stabilizers in PVC processing, as well as on the most toxic
653 organotin - tributyltin (TBT), used as a wood preservative (Mailhot et al., 1999). In the solid
654 digestate sampled from WWTPs, these compounds are detected at a level from 5.878 to 16.542
655 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S3**). In the case of the digestate originating from a WWTP, a decrease in MBT
656 concentration and an increase in TBT and DBT concentration was shown. Voulvoulis and
657 Lester (2006) conducted a laboratory-scale study and revealed that the degradation of TBT
658 during AD is minimal, which is associated with its high concentration in the sludge, having a
659 toxic effect on microorganisms responsible for carrying out the process. The removal efficiency
660 of TBT during AD was primarily related to the suspension removal efficiency and hence it is
661 expected to concentrate in the digestate.

662

663 **2.3. *Persistent contaminants in solid digestate***

664 **2.3.1. *Volatile methylsiloxanes (VMSs)***

665 VMSs are compounds containing silicon, oxygen, and methyl groups, which get into urban
666 wastewater as a result of the use of personal care products and also from industrial sources
667 (Silva et al., 2021). They include linear compounds (L3:L5) and cyclic compounds (D3:D6).
668 VMSs are found in the solid digestate in the concentration range from 0.009 to 4.1 mg kg⁻¹
669 (**Table S4**).

670 The research reveals that Σ VMSs can slightly decrease in effect of AD (from 3.8 mg kg⁻¹ in
671 a mixture of primary and secondary sludge to 3.58 mg kg⁻¹ in the non-dewatered digestate),
672 mainly due to the transfer of VMSs to the biogas (in particular, the most volatile congeners D3
673 and D4) and the degradation process (Silva et al., 2021). As a result of an elevated temperature
674 and the degradation of extracellular polymeric substances, VMSs are released from the
675 digestate (Ahn et al., 2014). In the non-dewatered digestate, the highest amounts of VMSs are
676 found in the case of D5, followed by D6, while the lowest ones for D4 and D3. In the dewatered
677 digestate, the amount of Σ VMSs is higher (5.7 mg kg⁻¹) than in the non-dewatered digestate
678 (**Fig. 3**). Silva et al. (2021) suggest that this is associated with the presence of a polymeric
679 solution added before centrifugation, which contains a siloxane base in its composition (Silva
680 et al., 2021). This may also be related to the resorption of the trapped biogas (Crone et al.,
681 2016). VMSs contained in the biogas can bind to extracellular polymeric substances, which
682 leads to their increased content in the dewatered digestate (Crone et al., 2016). The authors
683 (Silva et al., 2021) claim that a small part of VMSs may also go to the liquid fraction during
684 centrifugation, which particularly applies to more water-soluble VMSs.

685 The high stability of D4 and D5 during AD is explained by a comprehensive structure of
686 these compounds (Tansel and Surita, 2014). In the case of the D4 and D5 structure, the O atoms
687 are positioned inside the frame formed by the large Si atoms surrounded by methyl groups (-
688 CH₃), which makes their structures more stable and resistant to biodegradation during AD than
689 in the case of the D6 structures (Tansel and Surita, 2014). The high binding energy of Si-O and
690 its large length (1.64 Å), relative to the atomic sizes of the Si and O atoms, indicate that the Si
691 atoms, together with -CH₃ groups, provide a barrier, thus making it more difficult to break the
692 Si-O bonds (Tansel and Surita, 2014).

693

694 2.3.2. *Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs)*

695 PFASs consist of a carbon skeleton completely surrounded by fluorine atoms (Posner,
696 2012). Thanks to its ability to repel both water and oil molecules, they are ideal for surface
697 treatment. These compounds are used to produce paints, waxes, polishes, textiles, and food
698 packaging (Petrovic et al., 2013). The most frequently determined PFASs include
699 perfluorosulfonic acids (perfluorohexane sulfonate (PFHxS), perfluorooctane sulfonate
700 (PFOS), and perfluorodecane sulfonate (PFDS)) and perfluorocarboxylic acids
701 (perfluorooctanoate (PFOA), perfluorononanoate (PFNA), and perfluorodecanoate (PFDA)) as
702 well as 2-(N-methylperfluorooctanesulfonamido) acetic acid (N-MeFOSAA) and 2-(N-
703 ethylperfluorooctanesulfonamido) acetic acid (N-EtFOSAA). Their concentrations in the solid
704 digestate are in the range between 0.003 and 2.61 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S4**).

705 For a full-scale WWTP, Schulz et al. (2006) did not show changes in the content of PFDS
706 and PFDA during AD. It should however be emphasized that these authors observed an increase
707 in the content of some compounds (PFOS, N-MeFOSAA, N-EtFOSAA, and PFNA) at the
708 outlet of the digestion tank, which may be evidence of the degradation of their precursors during
709 the process (Schultz et al., 2006). Higgins et al. (2005) observed an increase in the concentration
710 of PFOA after AD, whereas Schulz et al. (2006) its decrease, which may evidence different
711 behaviors of the compound studied, depending on process conditions and sludge properties.
712 Based on theoretical calculations, Arvaniti et al. (2014) expected that during AD a major part
713 (> 76%) of the target PFASs would be adsorbed onto the solid digestate, while almost 3% of
714 PFOA would be detected in the liquid fraction. After a batch kinetic experiment, however, they
715 showed that only about 50% of the PFASs accumulated in the solid phase. It was also
716 demonstrated (Arvaniti et al., 2014) that the sorption ability of perfluorocarboxylic acids
717 towards the solid digestate increases with increasing perfluorocarbon chain length due to the
718 hydrophobic and oleophilic nature of the carbon-fluoride chain (**Fig. 3**). PFOS was

719 characterized by a higher sorption capacity than PFOA owing to the presence of one carbon
720 atom more in the chain and the presence of another functional group with higher acidity in the
721 molecule (sulfonic acid instead of carboxylic acid) (Arvaniti et al., 2014).

722

723 2.3.3. *Benzotriazoles*

724 Benzotriazoles are compounds that find wide applications as anticorrosive additives and
725 ultraviolet stabilizers in various commercial and industrial business areas (Cantwell et al.,
726 2015). The benzotriazole concentrations in the solid digestate range between 0.068 and 0.219
727 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S4**). Benzotriazole (BT) was detected at the highest level (0.196-0.219 mg kg⁻¹)
728 in the solid digestate, but its average content after AD exceeded those determined at the
729 beginning of the process (Liu et al., 2012). This indicates the resistance of BT to biological
730 degradation during MAD. A similar trend was observed for 5-chloro-benzotriazole (CBT), 5-
731 methyl-benzotriazole (5-TTri), and 5,6-dimethyl-benzotriazole (XTri), but only in the case of
732 AD carried out during the autumn period, because in the spring their content was found to
733 decrease after AD. This is not the first study that demonstrates that the season of the year has
734 an effect on the removal efficiency of different contaminants (**Fig. 3**). Furthermore, it was
735 shown that only a small part of CBT could be sorbed onto the solid digestate due to its relatively
736 low log K_{ow} (2.17) (Liu et al., 2012).

737

738 2.3.4. *Plant protection agents*

739 Plant protection agents are another groups of contaminants that are frequently found in the
740 solid digestate. The content of biocides, pesticides and herbicides in the solid digestate is at a
741 level from 0.003 to 0.24 mg kg⁻¹ (**Table S4**). In analyzing the fate of biocides (dichlorophene,

742 hexachlorophene, and fipronil), Heidler and Halden (2009) did not show AD to be effective in
743 their removal. Likewise, pesticides (diflubenzuron and hexaflumuron) (Heidler and Halden,
744 2009) and the herbicide diuron (DCMU) proved to be persistent compounds that are not
745 removed during AD (Yang et al., 2016). As the reasons for the difficulty in removing DCMU,
746 Yang et al. (2016) suggest the presence of chlorine and amide moieties in its structure, resulting
747 in strong electron-withdrawing, which causes its resistance to the AD process (**Fig. 3**). But a
748 similar phenomenon was not observed in other chlorinated contaminants (e.g. PCBs), which
749 were degraded to a certain extent during AD. It should however be stressed that also in the case
750 of PCBs their degradation range was determined by the number of chlorine substituents
751 (Gerardi, 2003).

752

753 **2.4. Contaminants in the liquid fraction of digestate**

754 The studies regarding the content of contaminants in the digestate liquid fraction are few in
755 comparison to the studies dealing with the solid residue. This is associated with the fact that
756 applications for the liquid fraction are currently being sought, because it is a product that opens
757 up possibilities of using it in different directions. While an entire sample is analyzed in the case
758 of the solid digestate (the result is expressed on a dry matter basis), which gives the actual
759 content of contaminants in this matrix and the potential losses caused by AD (excluding
760 adsorption), in the case of the liquid or gas fraction (described further on), apart from
761 degradation processes, losses of these compounds can result from their transfer to the other
762 elements of the system (**Fig. 4**). Therefore, they are not de facto only losses of individual
763 contaminants as a result of degradation processes, but rather the resultant of the transfer of
764 contaminants to the individual phases and the actual degradation. This transfer can depend on
765 a number of factors, but in the first place the water solubility (liquid fraction) and vapor pressure

766 of a compound (biogas) are important, as well as the affinity for the solid phase in both cases,
767 as expressed by $\log K_d$ or K_{oc} (matrix) and $\log K_{ow}$ (contaminant), among others. Therefore, the
768 losses of individual contaminants described in the next chapters will relate to the above-
769 mentioned processes.

770

771 **Fig. 4.** Transfer of organic contaminants to individual phases (solid, liquid and gas) during AD.

772 2.4.1. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)

773 Włodarczyk-Makuła (2008) conducted a study that determined the content of PAHs in the
774 liquid fraction during AD (**Table S5**). The liquid fraction was separated from the solid digestate
775 through centrifugation and decantation, whereas the PAH content was determined after liquid-
776 liquid extraction. After 7 days of the process, a 1.7- to 2.2-fold increase in the content of $\Sigma 16$
777 PAHs was found relative to the sludge liquid fraction, which may confirm the release of PAHs
778 strongly bound to the sludge into the liquid fraction. This can occur as a result of hydrolysis of
779 complex organic compounds. This process primarily involved 3- and 4-ring PAHs, while the

780 contents of 5- and 6-ring PAHs did not change significantly during AD. In the liquid fractions
781 taken from the bioreactor after 21 days of the experiment, the content of PAHs did not differ
782 significantly or was higher by 46% than the initial content of these compounds (depending on
783 the replicate). Włodarczyk-Makuła (2008) suggests that the decrease in PAHs in the liquid
784 fraction after 21 days of AD could have resulted from biotic and/or abiotic processes, but does
785 not give an explanation of the increase in PAH content over this time. The obtained results also
786 reveal large differences in the behavior of the PAHs depending on the replicate.

787

788 2.4.2. *Pharmaceuticals (PHACs)*

789 The studies (Ali et al., 2019; Carballa et al., 2007; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Malmborg and
790 Magnér, 2015; Yang et al., 2016) showed that in most cases PHACs have a higher affinity for
791 the solid digestate, but they also occur in certain amounts in the liquid fraction of the digestate.
792 Moreover, with increasing polarity of PHACs, there is a stronger transfer of these compounds
793 into the liquid fraction (Narumiya et al., 2013). The concentrations of PHACs in the liquid
794 fraction of the digestate range within wide limits and predominantly depend on the type of
795 compound (**Table S5**). When studying the digestate liquid fraction, a solution can be taken
796 directly from a biogas plant or WWTP (if they have such systems) (Ali et al., 2019; Genz and
797 Reemtsma, 2022), or it can be separated in a laboratory through centrifugation (Gonzalez-Gil
798 et al., 2016; Malmborg and Magnér, 2015; Yang et al., 2016).

799 Genz and Reemtsma (2022) analyzed PHACs with high polarity ($\log K_{ow} > 2$) in the liquid
800 fraction of the digestate. According to these authors, the highest removal efficiency from this
801 fraction was obtained for metformin (MET) (99.8% relative to the liquid fraction of the primary
802 sludge), which is in agreement with its reported biodegradability during AD (Campbell, 2013).
803 Moreover, Genz and Reemtsma (2022) revealed that during AD there was an increase in the

804 concentrations of 7 PHACs (CBZ, DCF, valsartan (VAL), gabapentin-lactam, lamotrigine,
805 metoprolol, and valsartan acid) in the liquid fraction of the digested sludge. Yang et al. (2016)
806 demonstrated that PHACs that are effectively removed from the liquid fraction of sewage
807 sludge during the AD process include CAF, ATN, PCM, and NPX. In the case of NPX,
808 Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) found that as much as 100% of this PHAC was eliminated from the
809 liquid fraction. On the other hand, CBZ, GEM, AMI, VE, and CZP exhibited no, or only slight,
810 biodegradation, whereas the IBP content in the liquid fraction was found to increase (Yang et
811 al., 2016).

812 In the study by Malmborg and Magnér (2015), after separation of the digestate into the
813 fractions, a higher IBP content was observed in the liquid fraction (83%) than in the solid
814 digestate. This is confirmed by the study by Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016), who showed that IBP
815 occurred in larger amounts in the solid fraction (62%) before AD, whereas after AD in the liquid
816 fraction (61%). According to Ali et al. (2019), levels and distribution profiles of contaminants
817 in digestates depend on various factors and ambient conditions (**Fig. 5**). They include the
818 following: the original contaminant profile in the substrate, physicochemical properties of
819 PHACs, and microbiological transformation processes during AD. Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016)
820 and Carballa et al. (2008), however, exclude the impact of the sludge type and AD process
821 parameters on the distribution of PHACs in the solid and liquid fractions of the digestate, which
822 is erroneous because sewage sludges can be characterized by a completely different
823 composition, both physical and biological, which will largely determine the stability
824 (persistence) of contaminants and their transfer to other elements of the system. Even more so
825 that it has been demonstrated that pH may affect the distribution of some PHACs between the
826 solid and liquid fractions during AD (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Narumiya et al., 2013). This
827 mainly applies to compounds that are ionizable, with a dissociation constant pK_a in the vicinity
828 of $pH = 5-7$ (Yang et al., 2016). At $pK_a = 4.9$, for instance, IBP may change its form from

829 moderately hydrophobic to hydrophilic, thus increasing its water solubility. In effect, a decrease
 830 in the concentration of IBP in the solid fraction during AD can result in a small but noticeable
 831 increase in its concentration in the aqueous fraction (Yang et al., 2016). Gonzalez-Gil et al.
 832 (2016) observed a similar situation in the case of DZP ($pK_a = 3.4$), for which the value of log
 833 K_d dropped after AD, which indicates growing affinity for the aqueous phase.

834

835 **Fig. 5.** Parameters affecting removal of organic compounds in liquid fraction.

836 Antibiotics are also detected in the digestate liquid fraction, and their concentration is
 837 determined by the type of compound (**Table S5**). Relatively low concentrations of antibiotics
 838 in the liquid fraction of the digestate are evidence of their low affinity for this fraction (Genz
 839 and Reemtsma, 2022; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2016). Overall, concentrations of
 840 antibiotics present in the sludge liquid fraction can increase or decrease after the AD process.
 841 The research reveals that application of AD to remove TMP (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2019; Yang
 842 et al., 2016) and SMX (Genz and Reemtsma, 2022) from the sludge liquid fraction can be
 843 effective. TMP is easily removed due to an amine group, capable of donating electrons, which
 844 it has in its structure (**Fig. 5**) (Yang et al., 2016). Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) showed the

845 parameters SRT and OLR to influence TMP and ROX removal under mesophilic and
846 thermophilic conditions. Furthermore, they demonstrated that the effectiveness of TMP
847 removal from the sludge liquid fraction depends on the season of the year and that it is more
848 efficient during the spring period (90-91%) than in autumn (<11%). SMX, in turn, due to its
849 high susceptibility to biodegradation (Carballa et al., 2007), can be completely removed from
850 the liquid fraction during AD, as shown by the study by Genz and Reemstma (2022). In the
851 case of ROX and CIP, an increase in their concentration after AD is noticeable (Genz and
852 Reemtsma, 2022; Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016).

853

854 2.4.3. *Bisphenol A (BPA)*

855 In the research carried out by Yang et al. (2016), BPA was detected in the digestate liquid
856 fraction at an amount of 25 or 43.75 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ at the SRT of 20 or 30 days, respectively (**Table**
857 **S5**). Contrary to the authors' expectations, the BPA content increased substantially (by 23.25-
858 42 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in the digestate liquid fraction after AD of the sludge. It had been expected that BPA
859 would be removed from the liquid fraction due to a strong electron-donating functional group
860 (hydroxyl) situated in the structure of this compound. The authors of the study (Yang et al.,
861 2016) proposed that the release of BPA from the plastic components of the experimental system
862 could be responsible for its elevated concentration.

863

864 2.4.4. *Estrogens*

865 Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016), as the only ones, additionally analyzed the content of E1, E2
866 and EE2 in the digestate liquid fraction. A substantial part of these compounds was absorbed
867 onto the solid fraction of the digestate, but their concentration in the liquid fraction was also

868 significant. In the digestate liquid fraction, it was detected at a level ranging between 0.073 μg
869 L^{-1} (E2) and 5.89 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (E1) (**Table S5**).

870 It is generally claimed that estrogens are removed from the liquid fraction to a small degree
871 during AD or their degradation is not observed at all. Depending on the sludge sampling time
872 (autumn or spring), Gonzalez-Gil et al. (2016) found a decrease (35-44%) or an increase (135-
873 466%) in the concentration of E1 in the liquid fraction both after MAD and TAD (**Fig. 5**). As
874 far as E2 is concerned, on the other hand, regardless of the sludge sampling time, its content in
875 the liquid fraction was found to increase after MAD (160-1502%) and TAD (6.2-793%). In the
876 case of EE2, an opposite trend was observed, i.e. the removal efficiency of this substance from
877 the liquid fraction during AD was more than 50%. The highest biodegradation of EE2 (88%)
878 was recorded for the sludge collected during the spring period and subjected to TAD. Gonzalez-
879 Gil et al. (2016) showed that EE2, as the only estrogen analyzed, was detected in larger amounts
880 in the liquid fraction (88%) after the AD process.

881 AD temperature was found to have an effect only in the case of EE2; the average
882 biotransformation was higher under TAD than for MAD (88 vs. 55%). In turn, the changes in
883 the estrogen content in the liquid fraction did not exhibit dependence on the parameters such as
884 SRT or OLR and the distribution of compounds between the fractions.

885

886 2.4.5. *Musk fragrances and personal care products*

887 Among musk fragrances, only HHCB was detected in the liquid fraction of the digestate
888 (6.91-9.79 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, **Table S5**). These substances are characterized by high hydrophobic
889 properties (Stasinakis, 2012), which hinders their quantification in the liquid fraction due to
890 their accumulation predominantly in the solid fraction (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016). Gonzalez-
891 Gil et al. (2016) revealed that the HHCB content in the liquid fraction did not change during

892 AD (an increase by 6.4% under TAD) or decreased (by 25% under MAD) (**Fig. 5**). Furthermore,
893 the authors (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016) demonstrated for HHCB that this compound goes into
894 the digestate liquid phase only in 10%.

895 The concentrations of personal care products in the liquid fraction of the digestate range
896 from 19.3 to 224 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (**Table S5**). In the case of TCS and TCC, no removal or only a slight
897 removal of these compounds from the liquid fraction during AD was shown (Yang et al., 2016).
898 The authors (Yang et al., 2016) explain that TCC is stable during AD because it has in its
899 structure chlorine and amide moieties, capable of strong electron withdrawal. In turn, Ali et al.
900 (2019) demonstrated, based on an analysis of the distribution profile of OCR, that it had an
901 untypically high affinity for the digestate liquid fraction. According to the authors (Ali et al.,
902 2019), given the high hydrophobicity of OCR, measured as $\log D = 6.34$ and $\log P = 7.53$, one
903 can expect that its major part will be found in the solid digestate.

904

905 2.4.6. *Linear alkylbenzene sulfonates (LASs)*

906 García et al. (2005), probably as the only ones, investigated the content of LASs in the
907 digestate liquid fraction. After adding C_{10} , C_{12} and C_{14} LASs to separate digestion tanks (32000
908 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), their sorption onto the digestate formed caused an increase in the concentration of the
909 LASs in the solid digestate and their substantial removal from the liquid fraction. The LAS
910 concentration in the digestate liquid fraction (**Table S5**) was 300 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (C_{14}), 2500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (C_{12}),
911 and 17100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (C_{10}), respectively, and hence it decreased significantly with increasing alkyl
912 chain length, i.e. with the increasing degree of LAS hydrophobicity.

913 In another study, García et al. (2006) revealed that the potential toxicity of LASs towards
914 anaerobic microorganisms is associated with the availability of these compounds in the
915 digestate liquid fraction. But in the study (García et al., 2005), a high degree of sorption of C_{14}

916 LAS onto the solid digestate was obtained, which caused a substantial decline in the
917 concentration of the surfactant in the liquid fraction of the digestate, thus reducing their
918 potential toxic effects on methanogenic bacteria.

919

920 2.4.7. *Benzotriazoles*

921 Benzotriazoles can occur in high concentrations in the liquid fraction of the digestate, as
922 shown by the study by Genz and Reemtsma (2022), who detected BT and its derivative, 4/5-
923 methylbenzotriazole (4/5-MBT), in the liquid fraction of the digestate at a level of 79.05 and
924 13.15 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively (**Table S5**). According to the results obtained by Genz and Reemtsma
925 (2022), both compounds increased their concentration in the liquid fraction after the AD process
926 by 130-354% (BT) and 174-287% (4/5-MBT), respectively, which indicates the ineffectiveness
927 of AD in removing these contaminants from the liquid fraction.

928

929 2.5. *Contaminants in biogas*

930 In the literature, there are particularly few studies dealing with the content of contaminants
931 in biogas. Research predominantly focuses on determining the energy value of biogas and the
932 content of gases in the biogas impacting its quality (e.g. CH_4 , CO_2 , H_2S) (Bragança et al., 2020;
933 Kabeyi and Olanrewaju, 2022). The scarcity of information regarding the content of organic
934 contaminants is primarily associated with their low vapor pressure and analytical difficulties.

935 2.5.1. *Hydrocarbons*

936 Benzene, toluene, xylenes, and methylated benzene compounds are aromatic hydrocarbons
937 that are commonly detected in biogas (Arnold and Kajolinna, 2010; Paolini et al., 2018; Rasi et
938 al., 2007). Rasi et al. (2007) report that the average benzene and toluene content in the biogas

939 ranges from 0.1 to 0.3 mg m⁻³ and from 2.8 to 11.8 mg m⁻³, respectively (**Table S6**). The higher
940 content of toluene than that of benzene probably results from the common use of toluene in
941 industry as a solvent, carrier, or thinner in cosmetics, paints, rubber, glues, printed materials,
942 and industrial resins, and hence its large amount gets into sewage (Rasi et al., 2007). Moreover,
943 Król and Holewa (2012) identified PAHs in biogas samples originating from a WWTP. The
944 content of Σ 12 PAHs in the biogas was shown not to exceed a level of 0.005 mg m⁻³. Comparing
945 the cancerogenicity of the compounds analyzed, the authors found that their amount obtained
946 should not pose a threat to the natural environment and biogas plant users. Furthermore, as far
947 as aliphatic hydrocarbons detected in biogas are concerned, compounds with 9-13 carbon atoms
948 (C₉-C₁₃) are found to have a predominance, among which Paolini et al. (2018) recorded the
949 highest content for compounds with 11 C atoms.

950

951 2.5.2. *Volatile methylsiloxanes (VMSs) and other organosilicon compounds*

952 VMSs are a common group of contaminants occurring in biogas (Werkneh, 2022). While
953 these compounds have not been found to have a harmful effect on the environment (Graiver et
954 al., 2003), the presence of VMSs in biogas is one of the obstacles to its use as an alternative
955 source of renewable energy. VMSs found in biogas are a group of secondary components
956 contributing to the inhibition of biomethane production (Tansel and Surita, 2014) as well as
957 they are responsible for contaminating post-combustion emissions-control catalytic systems
958 (Soreanu et al., 2011).

959 Linear compounds (L2:L5) and cyclic compounds (D3:D6) are VMSs that are most
960 frequently found in biogas (**Table S6**). Linear VMSs are detected at a lower level (< 0.001-1.29
961 mg m⁻³) than cyclic ones (0.016-27.05 mg m⁻³) (Arnold and Kajolinna, 2010; Ghidotti et al.,
962 2019; Oshita et al., 2010; Paolini et al., 2018; Tansel and Surita, 2014). L2, L3, and D3 are not

963 very common in biogas because they tend to volatilize from the sludge before AD due to their
964 high vapor pressure (Soreanu et al., 2011). D4 and D5 are VMSs that occur most frequently in
965 biogas. D5 alone, in particular, accounts for 27-91% of all VMSs analyzed on account of its
966 moderately high vapor pressure and boiling point (210°C) (Oshita et al., 2014). D6, on the other
967 hand, is characterized by a low vapor pressure and usually remains in the digestate (Paolini et
968 al., 2018; Soreanu et al., 2011), as evidenced by its low content in the biogas.

969 Oshita et al. (2014) confirmed the effectiveness of thermal treatment with gas stripping on
970 concentrated sewage sludge in reducing the content of VMSs in the sludge. By applying a
971 temperature of 80°C, about 90% of all VMSs in the sewage sludge was removed. AD carried
972 out in the next stage showed that the D5 content in the biogas from the optimally treated sludge
973 was 95% lower compared to the untreated sludge.

974 The results obtained by Arnold and Kajolinna (2010) reveal that also in the case of VMSs
975 the content of these contaminants in biogas is determined by the type of feedstock. For example,
976 the content of VMSs in the biogas was at a level of 0.03-27.05 mg m⁻³ (sewage sludge), 0.06-
977 4.46 mg m⁻³ (+ 30% kitchen waste/industrial sludge), or 0.03-1.29 mg m⁻³ (+ 30% municipal
978 and industrial bio-waste). Apart from that, the biogas produced from the amended sewage
979 sludge during AD exhibited a greater diversity of VMSs in comparison to AD of the unamended
980 sludge.

981 Moreover, trimethylsilanol (TMSOH), also belonging to the group of organosilicon
982 compounds, has been identified in biogas (Arnold and Kajolinna, 2010; Tansel and Surita,
983 2014). It is an organic chemical compound that contains the silicon-carbon bond (Si-C) and a
984 carboxyl group (-OH). Its content in the biogas is at a level between 0.02 and 0.075 mg m⁻³
985 (**Table S6**), i.e. a content similar to that of L2 and L3.

986

987 2.5.3. *Other contaminants*

988 Terpenes, such as limonene (Arnold and Kajolinna, 2010; Paolini et al., 2018), and amines
989 (2018) are also detected in biogas. In the case of the latter ones, no critical concentrations for
990 this group of compounds have been observed ($< 10 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$, **Table S6**).

991 According to Paolini et al. (2018), tetrachloroethylene is the only organochlorine compound
992 detected at a significant level. The low water solubility of this compound (0.15 g L^{-1}) leads to
993 its precipitation in the sewage sludge (Huang and Wang, 2014), and subsequently evaporation
994 into the biogas during AD (Paolini et al., 2018). Its frequent occurrence in biogas from sewage
995 sludge is confirmed by Chiriac et al. (2007). Paolini et al. (2018) found that the percentage of
996 tetrachloroethylene in the total chlorine content was marginal. This may probably be due to the
997 fact that chloroorganic compounds are present in the sewage sludge at a low level or can be
998 biodegraded during AD (Paolini et al., 2018). Moreover, its occurrence in the biogas may
999 probably arise from the application of AlCl_3 in the AD process (Paolini et al., 2018). Arnold
1000 and Kajolinna (2010) also detected halogens in the biogas, but at very low concentrations ($<$
1001 0.1 mg m^{-3}) (**Table S6**). It is moreover claimed that halogenated hydrocarbons, mainly chloro-
1002 , bromo- and fluoro-compounds, rarely occur in the biogas after sewage sludge AD (Werkneh,
1003 2022). It is important given the fact that these compounds are caustic and they can be precursors
1004 for the formation of dioxins and furans during biogas combustion (López et al., 2012).

1005

1006 **3. Dissipation pathways of contaminants during sewage sludge AD**

1007 During sewage sludge AD, contaminants can be degraded as a result of microbiological
1008 activity and also dissipated due to abiotic processes, such as leaching, volatilization,
1009 photodegradation, and the formation of transformed derivatives as a result of reactions with
1010 other compounds (Patureau and Trably, 2006; Włodarczyk-Makuła, 2008) (**Fig. 6**). At the same

1011 time, some organic contaminants can be strongly bound by organic matter, i.e. through
 1012 sequestration in solids of the digestate formed (Venegas et al., 2021) and bioaccumulation in
 1013 microorganisms (Dąbrowska and Rosińska, 2012) (**Fig. 6**).

1014

1015 **Fig. 6.** Fates of contaminants during sewage sludge AD.

1016 Biodegradation is often considered to be the dominant pathway for removal of organic
 1017 compounds from the sewage sludge during AD (Venegas et al., 2021). In the course of this
 1018 process, organic chemical substances are broken down into simpler compounds through the
 1019 activity of specialized microorganisms (Joutey et al., 2013). The term biodegradation is
 1020 frequently used interchangeably with the term biotransformation. This is of particular
 1021 importance during AD of PHACs, antibiotics, or estrogens, due to their conversion to
 1022 metabolites or intermediate products (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2019). Benabdallah El-Hadj et al.
 1023 (2007) reported that biodegradation largely contributed to the dissipation of PCBs in the solid
 1024 fraction of the sewage, especially PCB 180 during TAD (a 100% decrease in its content).
 1025 Furthermore, PHACs were shown to be characterized by equally high biodegradation. Samaras

1026 et al. (2014) observed the removal of DCF, KFN, NPX and IBF at a level from 76 to 96%. The
1027 biodegradation process was not significant in the case of VMSs, musk fragrances, personal care
1028 products, PFASs, and benzotriazoles. As regards musk fragrances, such as AHTN and HHCB,
1029 the highest concentration increases were found after AD (by 475 and 180%, respectively).
1030 Tansel and Surita (2014) explain the stability of VMSs, such as D4 and D5, during AD by their
1031 comprehensive structure. Yang et al. (2016) and Phan et al. (2018) demonstrated that the
1032 biodegradation of organic contaminants can be driven by their molecular structure. Compounds
1033 with electron-donating functional groups are easily degraded under AD, while compounds with
1034 electron-withdrawing capabilities are resistant during the process (Yang et al., 2016). Phan et
1035 al. (2018) also observed a high biotransformation rate for hydrophilic organic compounds with
1036 electron-donating functional groups.

1037 The second mechanism responsible for the dissipation of contaminants during AD is
1038 leaching. In the liquid fraction after AD, a decrease in the concentration of LASs, a decrease or
1039 no change in the content of musk fragrances and personal care products, a decrease or an
1040 increase in the concentrations of PAHs, PHACs and estrogens, and an increase in the
1041 concentrations of BPA, benzotriazoles and plant protection agents are observed. The increase
1042 in the concentrations of part of contaminants in the liquid fraction after AD may evidence the
1043 leaching of these compounds from the solid fraction during the process. In the case of PAHs
1044 and PHACs, a decrease in their content in the solid digestate has also been observed, which is
1045 caused by their leaching into the liquid fraction of the digestate. In the study by Włodarczyk-
1046 Makuła (2008), this process applied only to PAHs containing from 2 to 4 benzene rings in the
1047 molecule, which are characterized by a relatively high water solubility. On the other hand, the
1048 main property of PHACs that enables them to penetrate from the solid digestate into the liquid
1049 digestate is their polarity and possession of an electric charge (Ali et al., 2019). It is generally
1050 accepted that an increase in pH during AD is responsible for the transfer of PHACs between

1051 the solid and liquid fractions (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2016). The above cited
1052 authors explain this phenomenon based on the example of IBP and DZP; with increasing pH,
1053 they change their form from moderately hydrophobic to hydrophilic, thus increasing their water
1054 solubility, which results in their enhanced affinity for the liquid fraction of the digestate.

1055 Another mechanism responsible for decreasing the content of contaminants in the solid
1056 digestate/liquid fraction is the volatilization of compounds characterized by a high Henry's law
1057 constant and a high value of gas pressure into the biogas (Oshita et al., 2014; Silva et al., 2021;
1058 Włodarczyk-Makuła, 2008). The process of volatilization into the biogas during AD has been
1059 observed for PAHs and VMSs (**Fig. 7**).

1060 The sorption process depends on the physicochemical properties of suspended solids and
1061 chemical substances used as well as on ambient conditions, such as temperature, pH, ionic
1062 strength, or the presence of complexing agents (Stasinakis, 2012). Physically, it does not lead
1063 to the removal of contaminants but only reduces their mobility through their transfer from the
1064 liquid phase to the solid phase. This contributes to reducing their content in the liquid fraction
1065 (Stasinakis, 2012; Włodarczyk-Makuła, 2008). The impact of sorption can also be seen in the
1066 context of a change in the rate of biodegradation of contaminants, which is determined by their
1067 bioavailability (Stasinakis, 2012). Substances of hydrophobic nature (e.g. estrogens) are usually
1068 observed in sewage sludge and digestates at higher concentrations than substances of
1069 hydrophilic nature (e.g. PHACs) (Gonzalez-Gil et al., 2016). According to the study by
1070 Malmborg and Magner (2015), the stronger the hydrophobic properties a substance exhibits,
1071 the larger its amount is adsorbed onto the solid digestate. Similar observations were made by
1072 Garcia et al. (2005), who showed that the affinity of LASs for the digestate solid fraction rose
1073 with an extension of the LAS alkyl chain, i.e. with the increasing hydrophobicity of the
1074 compound.

1075

1076

1077 **Fig. 7.** The content of contaminants in solid digestate, liquid fraction and biogas (repeating
 1078 compounds are marked in color, other compounds are marked in grey).

1079

1080 **4. Future perspectives**

1081 To enhance the removal efficiency of contaminants from sewage sludge, efforts are made
1082 to optimize the AD process as best as possible. As far as certain issues are concerned, however,
1083 the knowledge regarding the fate of contaminants during sewage sludge AD is limited, which
1084 suggests that additional studies need to be conducted.

1085 • Many groups of contaminants have been detected in large amounts in sewage sludges,
1086 including microplastics (Liu et al., 2019; Murphy et al., 2016), nanoparticles (titanium
1087 dioxide and C₆₀ (fullerene) nanomaterials) (Wang et al., 2012), or illicit drugs (Baker and
1088 Kasprzyk-Hordern, 2013; Verovšek et al., 2023; Yadav et al., 2017). Because sewage
1089 sludge is the end point of most hydrophobic contaminants, but also of a substantial fraction
1090 of hydrophilic organic contaminants that have not been biotransformed during sewage
1091 treatment, it is highly likely that these groups of compounds will also be present in sewage
1092 sludge. The presence of illicit drugs (Mastroianni et al., 2013; Santana-Viera et al., 2023)
1093 and anticancer drugs (Dolu and Nas, 2023) in the sludge has already been confirmed in few
1094 studies. However, the lack of information regarding the removal of these contaminants
1095 during sludge AD is a gap in the knowledge, which leads to the absence of exact descriptions
1096 of the mechanisms of their degradation or methods of their dissipation.

1097 • In the case of some groups of contaminants (PAHs, PCBs), the AD process is effective in
1098 removing them. Nevertheless, compounds such as benzotriazoles are resistant to breakdown
1099 during sludge AD. It is therefore necessary to continuously optimize the process, to employ
1100 advanced pretreatment techniques, or to carry out co-digestion in the case of some
1101 contaminant groups in order to remove them.

1102 • When analyzing differences in concentrations before and after sewage sludge AD,
1103 assessment of the degree of distribution of contaminants without taking into consideration

1104 the mass balance in these calculations may lead to underestimation of the actual
1105 effectiveness of the removal process.

1106 • In most of the studies, only native compounds were analyzed, ignoring the semi-products
1107 formed during the process. An analysis of semi-products of organic contaminants would
1108 enable determination of a more exact mechanism of their removal during sewage sludge
1109 AD.

1110 • There is a complete lack of studies that would determine the distribution of contaminants
1111 simultaneously in the individual fractions (solid digestate, liquid fraction, and biogas).
1112 Conducting such an analysis would allow the distribution of contaminants between all AD
1113 products to be determined.

1114

1115 **5. Conclusions**

1116 In the literature, there are divergent opinions regarding the removal efficiency of
1117 contaminants during sewage sludge AD. Different contaminants are still present in most of the
1118 solid digestates, liquid fractions and biogas analyzed. Contaminants accumulate in the largest
1119 amount in the solid digestate, due to leaching, they can be transferred in small amounts to the
1120 liquid fraction. Moreover, volatile organic contaminants can volatilize from the sewage sludge
1121 into the biogas, with PAHs and VMSs being an example of that. The fate of contaminants is
1122 frequently influenced by process parameters, the type of sludge, and the characteristics of
1123 contaminants and their bioavailability. Research has revealed that biodegradation is of essential
1124 importance for removing organic compounds during AD, both from the solid fraction and the
1125 liquid fraction.

1126 Among organic contaminants, PCBs, PAHs, PHACs, and hydrocarbons are biodegraded to
1127 a certain extent in the solid fraction during AD, but contradictory results have been found for
1128 BPA, PAEs, NP and its derivatives, estrogens, musk fragrances, personal care products, LASs,
1129 and organotins. No significant removal of VMSs, PFASs, benzotriazoles, and plant protection
1130 agents has been observed, but on the contrary, even their elevated levels have been found in the
1131 solid digestate due to the decomposition of organic matter (mass reduction).

1132

1133 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

1134 **Wiktoria Blaszczyk:** Writing - original draft, Revision; **Anna Siatecka:** Writing - original
1135 draft; Writing - review & editing; **Pavel Tlustoš:** Writing - review & editing; **Patryk**
1136 **Oleszczuk:** Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Supervision.

1137 **Declaration of competing interest**

1138 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
1139 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

1140 **Data availability**

1141 Data will be made available on request.

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1145 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

1146 Supplementary data to this article can be found online at

1147 **References**

- 1148 Agarry, S., Oghenejoboh, K.M., 2015. Enhanced aerobic biodegradation of naphthalene in soil:
1149 Kinetic modelling and half-life study. *International Journal of Environmental*
1150 *Bioremediation & Biodegradation* 3, 48–53. <https://doi.org/10.12691/ijebb-3-2-2>
- 1151 Aguilar-Romero, I., Madrid, F., Villaverde, J., Morillo, E., 2024. Ibuprofen-enhanced
1152 biodegradation in solution and sewage sludge by a mineralizing microbial consortium.
1153 Shift in associated bacterial communities. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 464, 132970.
1154 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.132970>
- 1155 Ahel, M., Giger, W., Koch, M., 1994. Behaviour of alkylphenol polyethoxylate surfactants in
1156 the aquatic environment-I. Occurrence and transformation in sewage treatment. *Water*
1157 *Research* 28, 1131–1142. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354\(94\)90200-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354(94)90200-3)
- 1158 Ahn, Y.-M., Wi, J., Park, J.-K., Higuchi, S., Lee, N.-H., 2014. Effects of pre-aeration on the
1159 anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge. *Environmental Engineering Research* 19, 59–66.
1160 <https://doi.org/10.4491/eer.2014.19.1.059>
- 1161 Akinbomi, J.G., Patinvoh, R.J., Taherzadeh, M.J., 2022. Current challenges of high-solid
1162 anaerobic digestion and possible measures for its effective applications: A review.
1163 *Biotechnology for Biofuels and Bioproducts* 15, 52. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s13068-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13068-022-02151-9)
1164 [022-02151-9](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13068-022-02151-9)
- 1165 Al Seadi, T., Drosig, B., Fuchs, W., Rutz, D., Janssen, R., 2013. 12 - Biogas digestate quality
1166 and utilization, in: Wellinger, A., Murphy, J., Baxter, D. (Eds.), *The Biogas Handbook*,
1167 *Woodhead Publishing Series in Energy*. Woodhead Publishing, pp. 267–301.
1168 <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857097415.2.267>
- 1169 Ali, A.M., Nesse, A.S., Eich-Greatorex, S., Sogn, T.A., Aanrud, S.G., Aasen Bunæs, J.A.,
1170 Lyche, J.L., Kallenborn, R., 2019. Organic contaminants of emerging concern in
1171 Norwegian digestates from biogas production. *Environ. Sci.: Processes Impacts* 21,
1172 1498–1508. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EM00175A>

1173 Andersen, H., Siegrist, H., Halling-Sørensen, B., Ternes, T.A., 2003. Fate of estrogens in a
1174 municipal sewage treatment plant. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 37, 4021–4026.
1175 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es026192a>

1176 Aparicio, I., Santos, J.L., Alonso, E., 2009. Limitation of the concentration of organic pollutants
1177 in sewage sludge for agricultural purposes: A case study in South Spain. *Waste*
1178 *Management* 29, 1747–1753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2008.11.003>

1179 Appels, L., Baeyens, J., Degève, J., Dewil, R., 2008. Principles and potential of the anaerobic
1180 digestion of waste-activated sludge. *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science* 34,
1181 755–781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peccs.2008.06.002>

1182 Armstrong, D.L., Rice, C.P., Ramirez, M., Torrents, A., 2018. Fate of four phthalate plasticizers
1183 under various wastewater treatment processes. *J. Environ. Sci. Health. A. Tox. Hazard.*
1184 *Subst. Environ. Eng.* 53, 1075–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10934529.2018.1474580>

1185 Arnold, M., Kajolinna, T., 2010. Development of on-line measurement techniques for siloxanes
1186 and other trace compounds in biogas. *Waste Management* 30, 1011–1017.
1187 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2009.11.030>

1188 Arvaniti, O.S., Andersen, H.R., Thomaidis, N.S., Stasinakis, A.S., 2014. Sorption of
1189 perfluorinated compounds onto different types of sewage sludge and assessment of its
1190 importance during wastewater treatment. *Chemosphere* 111, 405–411.
1191 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.03.087>

1192 Baker, D.R., Kasprzyk-Hordern, B., 2013. Spatial and temporal occurrence of pharmaceuticals
1193 and illicit drugs in the aqueous environment and during wastewater treatment: New
1194 developments. *Science of The Total Environment* 454–455, 442–456.
1195 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.03.043>

1196 Bauer, T., Andreas, L., Lagerkvist, A., Burgman, L.E., 2020. Effects of the different
1197 implementation of legislation relating to sewage sludge disposal in the EU. *Detritus* 92–
1198 99. <https://doi.org/10.31025/2611-4135/2020.13944>

1199 Benabdallah El-Hadj, T., Dosta, J., Mata-Álvarez, J., 2006. Biodegradation of PAH and DEHP
1200 micro-pollutants in mesophilic and thermophilic anaerobic sewage sludge digestion.
1201 *Water science and technology: a journal of the International Association on Water
1202 Pollution Research* 53. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2006.240>

1203 Benabdallah El-Hadj, T., Dosta, J., Torres, R., Mata-Álvarez, J., 2007. PCB and AOX removal
1204 in mesophilic and thermophilic sewage sludge digestion. *Biochemical Engineering
1205 Journal* 36, 281–287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2007.03.001>

1206 Borja, J., Taleon, D.M., Auresenia, J., Gallardo, S., 2005. Polychlorinated biphenyls and their
1207 biodegradation. *Process Biochemistry* 40, 1999–2013.
1208 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2004.08.006>

1209 Bragança, I., Sánchez-Soberón, F., Pantuzza, G.F., Alves, A., Ratola, N., 2020. Impurities in
1210 biogas: Analytical strategies, occurrence, effects and removal technologies. *Biomass
1211 and Bioenergy* 143, 105878. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2020.105878>

1212 Campbell, A.J., 2013. The behaviour of pharmaceuticals in anaerobic digester sludge. Doctoral
1213 dissertation, University of Portsmouth.
1214 [https://researchportal.port.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/the-behaviour-of-pharmaceuticals-
1215 in-anaerobic-digester-sludge](https://researchportal.port.ac.uk/en/studentTheses/the-behaviour-of-pharmaceuticals-in-anaerobic-digester-sludge)

1216 Cantwell, M.G., Sullivan, J.C., Burgess, R.M., 2015. Chapter 16 - Benzotriazoles: History,
1217 Environmental Distribution, and Potential Ecological Effects, in: Zeng, E.Y. (Ed.),
1218 *Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry, Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs): Analytical
1219 Techniques, Environmental Fate and Biological Effects*. Elsevier, pp. 513–545.
1220 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63299-9.00016-8>

- 1221 Carballa, M., Fink, G., Omil, F., Lema, J.M., Ternes, T., 2008. Determination of the solid-water
1222 distribution coefficient (K_d) for pharmaceuticals, estrogens and musk fragrances in
1223 digested sludge. *Water Research* 42, 287–295.
1224 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2007.07.012>
- 1225 Carballa, M., Omil, F., Alder, A.C., Lema, J.M., 2006. Comparison between the conventional
1226 anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge and its combination with a chemical or thermal
1227 pre-treatment concerning the removal of pharmaceuticals and personal care products.
1228 *Water Sci Technol* 53, 109–117. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2006.241>
- 1229 Carballa, M., Omil, F., Ternes, T., Lema, J.M., 2007. Fate of pharmaceutical and personal care
1230 products (PPCPs) during anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge. *Water Research* 41,
1231 2139–2150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2007.02.012>
- 1232 Chang, B.V., Chang, S.W., Yuan, S.Y., 2003. Anaerobic degradation of polycyclic aromatic
1233 hydrocarbons in sludge. *Advances in Environmental Research, Sludge Management*
1234 *Entering the 3rd. Millennium* 7, 623–628. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1093-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1093-0191(02)00047-3)
1235 [0191\(02\)00047-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1093-0191(02)00047-3)
- 1236 Chen, Y., Cheng, J.J., Creamer, K.S., 2008. Inhibition of anaerobic digestion process: a review.
1237 *Bioresour Technol* 99, 4044–4064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2007.01.057>
- 1238 Chiriac, R., Carre, J., Perrodin, Y., Fine, L., Letoffe, J.-M., 2007. Characterisation of VOCs
1239 emitted by open cells receiving municipal solid waste. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*
1240 149, 249–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.07.094>
- 1241 Clara, M., Gans, O., Windhofer, G., Krenn, U., Hartl, W., Braun, K., Scharf, S., Scheffknecht,
1242 C., 2011. Occurrence of polycyclic musks in wastewater and receiving water bodies and
1243 fate during wastewater treatment. *Chemosphere* 82, 1116–1123.
1244 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2010.11.041>

1245 Crone, B.C., Garland, J.L., Sorial, G.A., Vane, L.M., 2016. Significance of dissolved methane
1246 in effluents of anaerobically treated low strength wastewater and potential for recovery
1247 as an energy product: A review. *Water Research* 104, 520–531.
1248 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.08.019>

1249 Czajka, C.P., Londry, K.L., 2006. Anaerobic biotransformation of estrogens. *Science of The*
1250 *Total Environment* 367, 932–941. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2006.01.021>

1251 Czekala, W., Jasiński, T., Grzelak, M., Witaszek, K., Dach, J., 2022. Biogas plant operation:
1252 digestate as the valuable product. *Energies* 15, 8275.
1253 <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15218275>

1254 Dąbrowska, L., Rosińska, A., 2012. Change of PCBs and forms of heavy metals in sewage
1255 sludge during thermophilic anaerobic digestion. *Chemosphere* 88, 168–173.
1256 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2012.02.073>

1257 De Simone, S., Di Capua, F., Pontoni, L., Giordano, A., Esposito, G., 2022. Impact of cationic
1258 polyelectrolyte addition on mesophilic anaerobic digestion and hydrocarbon content of
1259 sewage sludge. *Fermentation* 8, 548. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation8100548>

1260 Dictor, M.C., Berne, N., Mathieu, O., Moussay, A., Saada, A., 2003. Influence of ageing of
1261 polluted soils on bioavailability of phenanthrene. *Oil & Gas Science and Technology -*
1262 *Rev. IFP* 58, 481–488. <https://doi.org/10.2516/ogst:2003031>

1263 Dolu, T., Nas, B., 2023. Full-scale anaerobic digestion of sewage sludges: Fate evaluation of
1264 pharmaceuticals and main metabolites. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 51,
1265 103366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2022.103366>

1266 Dragicevic, I., Eich-Greatorex, S., Sogn, T.A., Horn, S.J., Krogstad, T., 2018. Use of high
1267 metal-containing biogas digestates in cereal production - Mobility of chromium and
1268 aluminium. *J Environ Manage* 217, 12–22.
1269 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.03.090>

1270 Fijalkowski, K., Rorat, A., Grobelak, A., Kacprzak, M.J., 2017. The presence of contaminations
1271 in sewage sludge – The current situation. *Journal of Environmental Management* 203,
1272 1126–1136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.05.068>

1273 Fountoulakis, M.S., Stamatelatou, K., Batstone, D.J., Lyberatos, G., 2006. Simulation of DEHP
1274 biodegradation and sorption during the anaerobic digestion of secondary sludge. *Water*
1275 *Sci Technol* 54, 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2006.533>

1276 Garcia, M.T., Campos, E., Dalmau, M., Illán, P., Sánchez-Leal, J., 2006. Inhibition of biogas
1277 production by alkyl benzene sulfonates (LAS) in a screening test for anaerobic
1278 biodegradability. *Biodegradation* 17, 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10532-005-2798->
1279 [x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10532-005-2798-x)

1280 García, M.T., Campos, E., Ribosa, I., Latorre, A., Sánchez-Leal, J., 2005. Anaerobic digestion
1281 of linear alkyl benzene sulfonates: Biodegradation kinetics and metabolite analysis.
1282 *Chemosphere* 60, 1636–1643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2005.02.048>

1283 Gebreyessus, G.D., Jenicek, P., 2016. Thermophilic versus mesophilic anaerobic digestion of
1284 sewage sludge: A comparative review. *Bioengineering (Basel)* 3, 15.
1285 <https://doi.org/10.3390/bioengineering3020015>

1286 Genz, P., Reemtsma, T., 2022. Polar micropollutants and metals in centrate from dewatered
1287 sewage sludge intended for reuse in soilless horticulture. *ACS EST Water* 2, 2548–
1288 2557. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsestwater.2c00345>

1289 Gerardi, M.H., 2003. *The microbiology of anaerobic digesters*, Wastewater microbiology
1290 series. Wiley-Interscience, Hoboken, N.J.

1291 Ghidotti, M., Fabbri, D., Torri, C., 2019. Determination of linear and cyclic volatile methyl
1292 siloxanes in biogas and biomethane by solid-phase microextraction and gas
1293 chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Talanta* 195, 258–264.
1294 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2018.11.032>

1295 Ghosh, S., Sahu, M., 2022. Phthalate pollution and remediation strategies: A review. *Journal of*
1296 *Hazardous Materials Advances* 6, 100065.
1297 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hazadv.2022.100065>

1298 González, M.M., Martín, J., Santos, J.L., Aparicio, I., Alonso, E., 2010. Occurrence and risk
1299 assessment of nonylphenol and nonylphenol ethoxylates in sewage sludge from
1300 different conventional treatment processes. *Science of The Total Environment* 408,
1301 563–570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2009.10.027>

1302 Gonzalez-Gil, L., Krah, D., Ghattas, A.-K., Carballa, M., Wick, A., Helmholz, L., Lema, J.M.,
1303 Ternes, T.A., 2019. Biotransformation of organic micropollutants by anaerobic sludge
1304 enzymes. *Water Research* 152, 202–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.12.064>

1305 Gonzalez-Gil, L., Papa, M., Feretti, D., Ceretti, E., Mazzoleni, G., Steimberg, N., Pedrazzani,
1306 R., Bertanza, G., Lema, J.M., Carballa, M., 2016. Is anaerobic digestion effective for
1307 the removal of organic micropollutants and biological activities from sewage sludge?
1308 *Water Research* 102, 211–220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.06.025>

1309 Gouda, A.M.R., Hagra, A.E., Okbah, M.A., El-Gammal, M.I., 2022. Influence of the linear
1310 alkylbenzene sulfonate (LAS) on hematological and biochemical parameters of Nile
1311 Tilapia, *Oreochromis niloticus*. *Saudi J Biol Sci* 29, 1006–1013.
1312 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.09.074>

1313 Graiver, D., Farminer, K.W., Narayan, R., 2003. A review of the fate and effects of silicones in
1314 the environment. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment* 11, 129–136.
1315 <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026056129717>

1316 Heidler, J., Halden, R.U., 2009. Fate of organohalogenes in US wastewater treatment plants and
1317 estimated chemical releases to soils nationwide from biosolids recycling. *J. Environ.*
1318 *Monit.* 11, 2207–2215. <https://doi.org/10.1039/B914324F>

1319 Herbes, C., Roth, U., Wulf, S., Dahlin, J., 2020. Economic assessment of different biogas
1320 digestate processing technologies: A scenario-based analysis. *Journal of Cleaner*
1321 *Production* 255, 120282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120282>

1322 Higgins, C.P., Field, J.A., Criddle, C.S., Luthy, R.G., 2005. Quantitative determination of
1323 perfluorochemicals in sediments and domestic sludge. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 39, 3946–
1324 3956. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es048245p>

1325 Huang, L.K., Wang, G.Z., 2014. Study on species and distribution of volatile organic
1326 compounds in WWTP. *Advanced Materials Research* 864–867, 2035–2038.
1327 <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.864-867.2035>

1328 Huynh, L.-H., Do, Q.-D., Kasim, N.S., Ju, Y.-H., 2011. Isolation and analysis of wax esters
1329 from activated sludge. *Bioresource Technology* 102, 9518–9523.
1330 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2011.08.005>

1331 Janex-Habibi, M.-L., Huyard, A., Esperanza, M., Bruchet, A., 2009. Reduction of endocrine
1332 disruptor emissions in the environment: the benefit of wastewater treatment. *Water Res*
1333 43, 1565–1576. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2008.12.051>

1334 Joutey, N.T., Bahafid, W., Sayel, H., ElGhachtouli, N., Joutey, N.T., Bahafid, W., Sayel, H.,
1335 ElGhachtouli, N., 2013. Biodegradation: Involved microorganisms and genetically
1336 engineered microorganisms, in: *Biodegradation - Life of Science*. IntechOpen.
1337 <https://doi.org/10.5772/56194>

1338 Kabeyi, M.J.B., Olanrewaju, O.A., 2022. Biogas production and applications in the sustainable
1339 energy transition. *Journal of Energy* 2022, e8750221.
1340 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8750221>

1341 Knudsen, L., Kristensen, G.H., Jørgensen, P.E., Jepsen, S.-E., 2000. Reduction of the content
1342 of organic micropollutants in digested sludge by a post-aeration process - a full-scale

1343 demonstration. *Water Science and Technology* 42, 111–118.
1344 <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2000.0183>

1345 Kovačić, Đ., Lončarić, Z., Jović, J., Samac, D., Popović, B., Tišma, M., 2022. Digestate
1346 management and processing practices: A review. *Applied Sciences* 12, 9216.
1347 <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12189216>

1348 Kreuzig, R., Haller-Jans, J., Bischoff, C., Leppin, J., Germer, J., Mohr, M., Bliedung, A.,
1349 Dockhorn, T., 2021. Reclaimed water driven lettuce cultivation in a hydroponic system:
1350 the need of micropollutant removal by advanced wastewater treatment. *Environ Sci*
1351 *Pollut Res* 28, 50052–50062. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-14144-6>

1352 Król, A., Holewa, J., 2012. Determination PAH in biogas. *Nafta-Gaz R.* 68, nr 12.

1353 Kuran, P., Trögl, J., Nováková, J., Pilařová, V., Dáňová, P., Pavlorková, J., Kozler, J., Novák,
1354 F., Popelka, J., 2014. Biodegradation of spilled diesel fuel in agricultural soil: Effect of
1355 humates, zeolite, and bioaugmentation. *The Scientific World Journal* 2014, 642427.
1356 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/642427>

1357 Lamastra, L., Suciú, N.A., Trevisan, M., 2018. Sewage sludge for sustainable agriculture:
1358 Contaminants' contents and potential use as fertilizer. *Chemical and Biological*
1359 *Technologies in Agriculture* 5, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40538-018-0122-3>

1360 Lehmann, L., Bloem, E., 2021. Antibiotic residues in substrates and output materials from
1361 biogas plants – Implications for agriculture. *Chemosphere* 278, 130425.
1362 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130425>

1363 Liew, C.S., Yunus, N.M., Chidi, B.S., Lam, M.K., Goh, P.S., Mohamad, M., Sin, J.C., Lam,
1364 S.M., Lim, J.W., Lam, S.S., 2022. A review on recent disposal of hazardous sewage
1365 sludge via anaerobic digestion and novel composting. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*
1366 423, 126995. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126995>

- 1367 Lin, R., Cheng, J., Ding, L., Murphy, J.D., 2018. Improved efficiency of anaerobic digestion
1368 through direct interspecies electron transfer at mesophilic and thermophilic temperature
1369 ranges. *Chemical Engineering Journal* 350, 681–691.
1370 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2018.05.173>
- 1371 Liu, X., Yuan, W., Di, M., Li, Z., Wang, J., 2019. Transfer and fate of microplastics during the
1372 conventional activated sludge process in one wastewater treatment plant of China.
1373 *Chemical Engineering Journal* 362, 176–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.01.033>
- 1374 Liu, Y.-S., Ying, G.-G., Shareef, A., Kookana, R.S., 2012. Occurrence and removal of
1375 benzotriazoles and ultraviolet filters in a municipal wastewater treatment plant. *Environ*
1376 *Pollut* 165, 225–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2011.10.009>
- 1377 López, M.E., Rene, E.R., Veiga, M.C., Kennes, C., 2012. Biogas technologies and cleaning
1378 techniques, in: Lichtfouse, E., Schwarzbauer, J., Robert, D. (Eds.), *Environmental*
1379 *Chemistry for a Sustainable World: Volume 2: Remediation of Air and Water Pollution,*
1380 *Environmental Chemistry for a Sustainable World.* Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht,
1381 pp. 347–377. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-2439-6_9
- 1382 Mailhot, G., Astruc, M., Bolte, M., 1999. Degradation of tributyltin chloride in water
1383 photoinduced by iron (III). *Applied Organometallic Chemistry* 13, 53–61.
1384 [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-0739\(199901\)13:1<53::AID-AOC814>3.0.CO;2-5](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-0739(199901)13:1<53::AID-AOC814>3.0.CO;2-5)
- 1385 Malmborg, J., Magnér, J., 2015. Pharmaceutical residues in sewage sludge: Effect of
1386 sanitization and anaerobic digestion. *Journal of Environmental Management* 153, 1–10.
1387 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2015.01.041>
- 1388 Marttinen, S.K., Kettunen, R.H., Sormunen, K.M., Rintala, J.A., 2003. Removal of bis(2-
1389 ethylhexyl) phthalate at a sewage treatment plant. *Water Research* 37, 1385–1393.
1390 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(02\)00486-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(02)00486-4)

1391 Massé, D.I., Saady, N.M.C., Gilbert, Y., 2014. Potential of biological processes to eliminate
1392 antibiotics in livestock manure: An overview. *Animals* 4, 146–163.
1393 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani4020146>

1394 Mastroianni, N., Postigo, C., De Alda, M.L., Barcelo, D., 2013. Illicit and abused drugs in
1395 sewage sludge: Method optimization and occurrence. *Journal of Chromatography A*
1396 1322, 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2013.10.078>

1397 Minamiyama, M., Ochi, S., Suzuki, Y., 2006. Fate of nonylphenol polyethoxylates and
1398 nonylphenoxy acetic acids in an anaerobic digestion process for sewage sludge
1399 treatment. *Water Sci Technol* 53, 221–226. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2006.356>

1400 Montano, L., Pironti, C., Pinto, G., Ricciardi, M., Buono, A., Brogna, C., Venier, M., Piscopo,
1401 M., Amoresano, A., Motta, O., 2022. Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in the
1402 environment: Occupational and exposure events, effects on human health and fertility.
1403 *Toxics* 10, 365. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics10070365>

1404 Moreda, J.M., Arranz, A., Fdez De Betoño, S., Cid, A., Arranz, J.F., 1998. Chromatographic
1405 determination of aliphatic hydrocarbons and polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in a
1406 sewage sludge. *Science of The Total Environment* 220, 33–43.
1407 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697\(98\)00238-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697(98)00238-1)

1408 Mulchandani, A., Westerhoff, P., 2016. Recovery opportunities for metals and energy from
1409 sewage sludges. *Bioresource Technology, Waste Biorefinery - Advocating Circular*
1410 *Economy* 215, 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.03.075>

1411 Murphy, F., Ewins, C., Carbonnier, F., Quinn, B., 2016. Wastewater treatment works (WwTW)
1412 as a source of microplastics in the aquatic environment. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50,
1413 5800–5808. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b05416>

1414 Narumiya, M., Nakada, N., Yamashita, N., Tanaka, H., 2013. Phase distribution and removal
1415 of pharmaceuticals and personal care products during anaerobic sludge digestion. *J*
1416 *Hazard Mater* 260, 305–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2013.05.032>

1417 Obiukwu, O., Okafor, I. M., 2013. Determination of the mesophilic temperature for optimum
1418 continuous process biogas production from anaerobic digestion of animal wastes. *The*
1419 *Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, 14.

1420 Oleszczuk, P., Baran, S., 2003. Degradation of individual polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
1421 (PAHs) in soil polluted with aircraft fuel. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*, 12.

1422 Oshita, K., Ishihara, Y., Takaoka, M., Takeda, N., Matsumoto, T., Morisawa, S., Kitayama, A.,
1423 2010. Behaviour and adsorptive removal of siloxanes in sewage sludge biogas. *Water*
1424 *Science and Technology* 61, 2003–2012. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2010.101>

1425 Oshita, K., Omori, K., Takaoka, M., Mizuno, T., 2014. Removal of siloxanes in sewage sludge
1426 by thermal treatment with gas stripping. *Energy Conversion and Management* 81, 290–
1427 297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2014.02.050>

1428 Paolini, V., Petracchini, F., Carnevale, M., Gallucci, F., Perilli, M., Esposito, G., Segreto, M.,
1429 Occulti, L.G., Scaglione, D., Ianniello, A., Frattoni, M., 2018. Characterisation and
1430 cleaning of biogas from sewage sludge for biomethane production. *Journal of*
1431 *Environmental Management* 217, 288–296.
1432 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.03.113>

1433 Paterakis, N., Chiu, T.Y., Koh, Y.K.K., Lester, J.N., McAdam, E.J., Scrimshaw, M.D., Soares,
1434 A., Cartmell, E., 2012. The effectiveness of anaerobic digestion in removing estrogens
1435 and nonylphenol ethoxylates. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 199–200, 88–95.
1436 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2011.10.075>

1437 Patureau, D., Delgenes, N., Delgenes, J.-P., 2008. Impact of sewage sludge treatment processes
1438 on the removal of the endocrine disrupters nonylphenol ethoxylates. *Chemosphere* 72,
1439 586–591. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2008.03.007>

1440 Patureau, D., Trably, E., 2006. Impact of anaerobic and aerobic processes on
1441 polychlorobiphenyl removal in contaminated sewage sludge. *Biodegradation* 17, 9–17.
1442 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10532-005-1920-4>

1443 Petrovic, M., Farré, M., Eljarrat, E., Diaz, S., Barceló, D., 2013. Chapter 14 - Environmental
1444 analysis: Emerging pollutants, in: Fanali, S., Haddad, P.R., Poole, C.F., Schoenmakers,
1445 P., Lloyd, D. (Eds.), *Liquid Chromatography*. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 389–410.
1446 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-415806-1.00014-0>

1447 Phan, H.V., Wickham, R., Xie, S., McDonald, J.A., Khan, S.J., Ngo, H.H., Guo, W., Nghiem,
1448 L.D., 2018. The fate of trace organic contaminants during anaerobic digestion of
1449 primary sludge: A pilot scale study. *Bioresource Technology* 256, 384–390.
1450 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2018.02.040>

1451 Pigoli, A., Zilio, M., Tambone, F., Mazzini, S., Schepis, M., Meers, E., Schoumans, O.,
1452 Giordano, A., Adani, F., 2021. Thermophilic anaerobic digestion as suitable bioprocess
1453 producing organic and chemical renewable fertilizers: A full-scale approach. *Waste*
1454 *Management* 124, 356–367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.02.028>

1455 Posner, S., 2012. Perfluorinated compounds: Occurrence and uses in products, in: Knepper,
1456 T.P., Lange, F.T. (Eds.), *Polyfluorinated Chemicals and Transformation Products*, The
1457 *Handbook of Environmental Chemistry*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 25–39.
1458 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-21872-9_2

1459 Rasi, S., Veijanen, A., Rintala, J., 2007. Trace compounds of biogas from different biogas
1460 production plants. *Energy* 32, 1375–1380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2006.10.018>

- 1461 Samaras, V.G., Stasinakis, A.S., Thomaidis, N.S., Mamais, D., Lekkas, T.D., 2014. Fate of
1462 selected emerging micropollutants during mesophilic, thermophilic and temperature co-
1463 phased anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge. *Bioresource Technology* 162, 365–372.
1464 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2014.03.154>
- 1465 Santana-Viera, S., Pintado-Herrera, M.G., Sosa-Ferrera, Z., Santana-Rodríguez, J.J., 2023.
1466 Analysis of psychoactive substances and metabolites in sludges, soils, sediments and
1467 biota: a review. *Environ Chem Lett* 21, 2311–2335. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-023-01586-2)
1468 [023-01586-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-023-01586-2)
- 1469 Santos, J.L., González, M.D.M., Aparicio, I., Alonso, E., 2007. Monitoring of di-(2-
1470 ethylhexyl)phthalate, nonylphenol, nonylphenol ethoxylates, and polychlorinated
1471 biphenyls in anaerobic and aerobic sewage sludge by gas chromatography–mass
1472 spectrometry. *International Journal of Environmental Analytical Chemistry* 87, 1033–
1473 1042. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03067310701616556>
- 1474 Schultz, M.M., Higgins, C.P., Huset, C.A., Luthy, R.G., Barofsky, D.F., Field, J.A., 2006.
1475 Fluorochemical mass flows in a municipal wastewater treatment facility. *Environ. Sci.*
1476 *Technol.* 40, 7350–7357. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es061025m>
- 1477 Siebielska, I., 2014. Comparison of changes in selected polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
1478 concentrations during the composting and anaerobic digestion processes of municipal
1479 waste and sewage sludge mixtures. *Water Science and Technology* 70, 1617–1624.
1480 <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2014.417>
- 1481 Silva, J., Bernardo, F., Jesus, M., Faria, T., Alves, A., Ratola, N., Homem, V., 2021. Levels of
1482 volatile methylsiloxanes in urban wastewater sludges at various steps of treatment.
1483 *Environ Chem Lett* 19, 2723–2732. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10311-021-01191-1>

1484 Sinkkonen, S., Paasivirta, J., 2000. Degradation half-life times of PCDDs, PCDFs and PCBs
1485 for environmental fate modeling. *Chemosphere* 40, 943–949.
1486 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-6535\(99\)00337-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-6535(99)00337-9)

1487 Soreanu, G., Béland, M., Fallettal, P., Edmonson, K., Svoboda, L., Al-Jamal, M., Seto, P., 2011.
1488 Approaches concerning siloxane removal from biogas—A review. *Canadian Biosystem*
1489 *Engineering Journal* 53, 8.1-8.18.

1490 Stasinakis, A.S., 2012. Review on the fate of emerging contaminants during sludge anaerobic
1491 digestion. *Bioresource Technology* 121, 432–440.
1492 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2012.06.074>

1493 Taboada-Santos, A., Braz, G.H.R., Fernandez-Gonzalez, N., Carballa, M., Lema, J.M., 2019.
1494 Thermal hydrolysis of sewage sludge partially removes organic micropollutants but
1495 does not enhance their anaerobic biotransformation. *Science of The Total Environment*
1496 690, 534–542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.492>

1497 Tambone, F., Orzi, V., D’Imporzano, G., Adani, F., 2017. Solid and liquid fractionation of
1498 digestate: Mass balance, chemical characterization, and agronomic and environmental
1499 value. *Bioresource Technology* 243, 1251–1256.
1500 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.07.130>

1501 Tansel, B., Surita, S.C., 2014. Differences in volatile methyl siloxane (VMS) profiles in biogas
1502 from landfills and anaerobic digesters and energetics of VMS transformations. *Waste*
1503 *Management* 34, 2271–2277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2014.07.025>

1504 Ternes, T.A., Andersen, H., Gilberg, D., Bonerz, M., 2002. Determination of estrogens in
1505 sludge and sediments by liquid extraction and GC/MS/MS. *Anal. Chem.* 74, 3498–
1506 3504. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac015717z>

1507 Trably, E., Patureau, D., Delgenes, J.P., 2003. Enhancement of polycyclic aromatic
1508 hydrocarbons removal during anaerobic treatment of urban sludge. *Water Sci Technol*
1509 48, 53–60.

1510 Usman, K., Khan, S., Ghulam, S., Khan, M.U., Khan, N., Khan, M.A., Khalil, S.K., 2012.
1511 Sewage sludge: An important biological resource for sustainable agriculture and its
1512 environmental implications. *AJPS* 03, 1708–1721.
1513 <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajps.2012.312209>

1514 Vasiljevic, T., Harner, T., 2021. Bisphenol A and its analogues in outdoor and indoor air:
1515 Properties, sources and global levels. *Science of The Total Environment* 789, 148013.
1516 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.148013>

1517 Venegas, M., Leiva, A.M., Reyes-Contreras, C., Neumann, P., Piña, B., Vidal, G., 2021.
1518 Presence and fate of micropollutants during anaerobic digestion of sewage and their
1519 implications for the circular economy: A short review. *Journal of Environmental*
1520 *Chemical Engineering* 9, 104931. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.104931>

1521 Verovšek, T., Šuštarich, A., Laimou-Geraniou, M., Krizman-Matasic, I., Prosen, H., Eleršek, T.,
1522 Kramarič Zidar, V., Mislej, V., Mišmaš, B., Stražar, M., Levstek, M., Cimrmančič, B.,
1523 Lukšič, S., Uranjek, N., Kozlovič-Bobič, T., Kosjek, T., Kocman, D., Heath, D., Heath,
1524 E., 2023. Removal of residues of psychoactive substances during wastewater treatment,
1525 their occurrence in receiving river waters and environmental risk assessment. *Science*
1526 *of The Total Environment* 866, 161257.
1527 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.161257>

1528 Voulvoulis, N., Lester, J.N., 2006. Fate of organotins in sewage sludge during anaerobic
1529 digestion. *Sci Total Environ* 371, 373–382.
1530 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2006.08.024>

1531 Walters, E., McClellan, K., Halden, R.U., 2010. Occurrence and loss over three years of 72
1532 pharmaceuticals and personal care products from biosolids–soil mixtures in outdoor
1533 mesocosms. *Water Research* 44, 6011–6020.
1534 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2010.07.051>

1535 Wang, Y., Qian, H., 2021. Phthalates and their impacts on human health. *Healthcare (Basel)* 9,
1536 603. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9050603>

1537 Wang, Y., Westerhoff, P., Hristovski, K.D., 2012. Fate and biological effects of silver, titanium
1538 dioxide, and C₆₀ (fullerene) nanomaterials during simulated wastewater treatment
1539 processes. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 201–202, 16–22.
1540 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2011.10.086>

1541 Werkneh, A.A., 2022. Biogas impurities: environmental and health implications, removal
1542 technologies and future perspectives. *Heliyon* 8, e10929.
1543 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10929>

1544 Wiegel, J., Wu, Q., 2000. Microbial reductive dehalogenation of polychlorinated biphenyls.
1545 *FEMS Microbiology Ecology* 32, 1–15. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-6496\(00\)00014-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-6496(00)00014-3)
1546 3

1547 Włodarczyk-Makuła, M., 2008. PAHs balance in solid and liquid phase of sewage sludge
1548 during fermentation process. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part A* 43,
1549 1602–1609. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10934520802329869>

1550 Xiao, L., Wang, Y., Lichtfouse, E., Li, Z., Kumar, P.S., Liu, J., Feng, D., Yang, Q., Liu, F.,
1551 2021. Effect of antibiotics on the microbial efficiency of anaerobic digestion of
1552 wastewater: A review. *Front Microbiol* 11, 611613.
1553 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.611613>

- 1554 Yadav, M.K., Short, M.D., Aryal, R., Gerber, C., van den Akker, B., Saint, C.P., 2017.
1555 Occurrence of illicit drugs in water and wastewater and their removal during wastewater
1556 treatment. *Water Research* 124, 713–727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.07.068>
- 1557 Yang, J.-F., Ying, G.-G., Yang, L.-H., Zhao, J.-L., Liu, F., Tao, R., Yu, Z.-Q., Peng, P., 2009.
1558 Degradation behavior of sulfadiazine in soils under different conditions. *Journal of*
1559 *Environmental Science and Health, Part B* 44, 241–248.
1560 <https://doi.org/10.1080/03601230902728245>
- 1561 Yang, S., Hai, F.I., Price, W.E., McDonald, J., Khan, S.J., Nghiem, L.D., 2016. Occurrence of
1562 trace organic contaminants in wastewater sludge and their removals by anaerobic
1563 digestion. *Bioresource Technology, Special Issue on Challenges in Environmental*
1564 *Science and Engineering (CESE-2015)* 210, 153–159.
1565 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2015.12.080>
- 1566 Zhang, Z.-M., Zhang, J., Zhang, H.-H., Shi, X.-Z., Zou, Y.-W., Yang, G.-P., 2020. Pollution
1567 characteristics, spatial variation, and potential risks of phthalate esters in the water–
1568 sediment system of the Yangtze River estuary and its adjacent East China Sea.
1569 *Environmental Pollution* 265, 114913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.114913>
- 1570 Zhu, Y., Zheng, G., Gao, D., Chen, T., Wu, F., Niu, M., Zou, K., 2016. Odor composition
1571 analysis and odor indicator selection during sewage sludge composting. *Journal of the*
1572 *Air & Waste Management Association* 66, 930–940.
1573 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2016.1188865>
- 1574